

Methods to record agroforestry areas and greenhouse gas emissions in the EU

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Scope: The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide actors with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three targeted actor groups are: a) **policy actors:** policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry; b) **practitioners:** farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond, c) **beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services:** stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry systems, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms. Type your text

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Abbreviations

AFOLU: Agriculture Forestry and Other Land Use

BISS: Basic Income Support for Sustainability

CFCR: Certification Framework for Carbon Removals

CORINE: Coordination of information on the environment

IACS: Integrated Administration and Control System

IUCN: International Union for the Conservation of Nature

LiDAR: Light Detection and Ranging (using laser light to measure distances and 3D models)

LPIS: Land Parcel Information System

LUCAS: Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey

LULUCF: Land Use Land Use Change and Forestry

NFI: National Forest Inventory

ToF: Trees outside Forests

UNFCCC: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

1. Introduction

Agroforestry has a significant climate change mitigation potential because of its capacity to store carbon in biomass and soil. Natural forests also have a high potential for carbon accumulation (Toensmeier 2016; Cook-Patton et al. 2020) because of the high density of trees in forests. Of all man-made systems, agroforestry is among those systems which store high amounts of carbon (Mohan Kumar & Ramachandran Nair 2011; Toensmeier 2016). Tropical home gardens store large amounts of carbon, in particular. Temperate agroforestry systems store less carbon compared to tropical systems, but as a large part of Europe is covered by agriculture (about 40% of the total land area (Eurostat 2022)), converting agricultural land to agroforestry would have enormous potential of storing additional carbon. Even in the boreal region, where carbon storage is relatively limited due to slow growth, the potential is large due to the vastness of this area. Therefore, it is important to develop a more harmonized, standardized, and reliable estimate of the current extent of agroforestry to more precisely assess the amount of carbon currently stored in agroforestry systems and its future potential.

In this report, we will focus on existing methods which are used or could be used in estimating agroforestry areas with a focus on Europe in particular. Multiple pressures on European Forests make it more important than ever to recognise the importance of Trees outside Forests (ToF) and to ensure that they are managed not just for

environmental and climate-change mitigation, but for productive timber and agricultural services. This report first defines what EU Member States mean by "agroforestry" and "woody landscape features", then it examines eight approaches to quantification of this resource, often used in combination:

- LUCAS data (Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey)
- NFI - National Forest Inventories
- CAP Integrated Administration and Control - Geospatial datasets - LPIS/GSAA
- CORINE (Coordination of Information on the Environment) Land Cover Data
- EU Forest Observatory Global Forest Map
- Copernicus Tree Cover Density datasets
- UNFCCC National Inventory Reports from EU Member States
- Orthophotos and LiDAR - used to locate individual trees

The final sections in the report consider upcoming legislation, including a) the next Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and the requirement identified in the DGAGRI "Vision for Agriculture and Food" to establish an on-farm "Sustainability Compass" to hold farm-level information on environmental, social and financial sustainability, b) the upcoming requirements of voluntary carbon farming certification with details held in a geospatial registry, and c) options for the EU Emission Trading Scheme to be extended to include agriculture and forestry (as "ETS-3") - which will require comprehensive mapping of agricultural, forest and agroforestry parcels.

2. Definitions of agroforestry and landscape features - improvements needed in Member States

The European Union in its Rural Development Regulation (Regulation 1305/2013) defined agroforestry as "land use systems in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land". All Member States (MS) were required to provide national definitions of agroforestry in their CAP Strategic Plans (EURAF Policy Briefing #22 - (Lawson 2023a), and the Strategic Plan Regulation (Regulation 2021/2115) makes it clear that "agroforestry" should be included within the national definitions of agricultural land.¹

- **Recital 14** indicates that "the framework definitions of 'agricultural area' should ensure that Member States cover agroforestry systems, where trees are grown in agricultural parcels on which agricultural activities are carried out to improve the sustainable use of the land"
- **Article 4(3)** indicates that "Agricultural area" shall be determined in such a way as to comprise arable land, permanent crops and permanent grassland, **including when they form agroforestry systems on that area**".

Agroforestry also occurs on forest land, normally in the form of shifting "forest-grazing". This would not normally be considered a land use. The EURAF Agroforestry Typology (Table 1) divides all rural areas in the EU into "agricultural land" and "forest land", then splits the former into "arable land", "permanent grassland" and "permanent crops". The classification also recognises the "Land Parcel Information System" (LPIS) of EU Member States which records "Landscape Features", including hedges, individual trees, lines of trees and groups of trees as a separate land-use category. Whereas Landscape Features are protected by Member States and are guaranteed to receive full CAP area payments, agroforestry areas may have their basic payments reduced by MS according to assessments of the shading cast by mature trees, or the area occupied by tree-rows of young trees. In all MS, with the partial exception of Spain, area-payments are not made for "forest" land, although they can be eligible for "rural development" assistance in Pillar II of the CAP.

¹ The exception to this is Ireland, where new agroforestry plantations are treated as "**forest land**", despite remaining eligible for CAP Pillar I agricultural Basic Payments (BISS) throughout the life of the plantation. This creates an apparent contradiction with the Irish CAP Strategic Plan Regulation which says that agroforestry as "the combination of arable land/permanent crops/permanent grassland and forestry shall be deemed an **agricultural area**".

Table 1: Agroforestry Typology of the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF Policy Briefing #1 - (Worms & Lawson 2020)

Tree location	Agroforestry System	Agroforestry Practice	
		Agricultural Land	Forest Land
<i>Trees inside parcels</i>	Silvopastoral agroforestry	1 Wood pasture	10 Forest grazing
	Silvoarable agroforestry	2 Alley cropping 3 Alley coppice 4 Food forests	4 Food forests
	Permanent crop agroforestry	5 Orchard cropping, 6 Orchard grazing.	
	Agro-silvo-pasture	7 Agro-silvo-pasture	
<i>Trees between parcels</i>	Tree Landscape Features (protected by CAP Conditionality Rules)	8 Woody-landscape-features	
<i>Trees in settlements</i>	Urban agroforestry	9. Settlement agroforestry	

2.1 Silvopastoral systems

Silvopastoralism integrates trees, livestock, and forage production on the same land, simultaneously or in a sequential way (Nair 1993). In Europe, it includes cultivated (sown) or natural (self-seeded) pasture with planted and/or naturally regenerated trees in various arrangements (Bergmeier et al. 2010; Cabbage et al. 2012; Plieninger et al. 2015). Silvopastoralism can include the following practices (Table 1).

- **Wood-pasture** - where trees are combined with permanent grassland. Permanent grassland is land which has not been cultivated for at least 5-years, and which is used to grow herbaceous fodder, forage or energy-crops (EUROSTAT 2023b). Some countries (e.g. Spain, Ireland and Greece) classify extensive areas of shrubs or dwarf shrubs as "permanent grassland", even if there is no herbaceous vegetation present (Bertomeu & Lawson 2023; Reid et al. 2008; Ruiz et al. 2019).
- **Orchard grazing** (i.e. grazing in "permanent crops") - includes grassland beneath all fruit trees, citrus fruit trees, nut trees (including pine-nuts and chestnuts), berry plantations, vineyards, olive trees and all other permanent crops used for human consumption (e.g. tea, coffee or carobs in some overseas territories) (EUROSTAT 2023a);
- **Agro-silvo-pasture** - where silvopasture replaces a silvoarable system as the trees become larger, or where grazing and cropping are alternated.
- **Forest-grazing** - where grazing is practised on land which is classified nationally as "forest".

Silvopastoralism has been practised in Europe for millenia. It covers a large proportion of the territory and has shaped landscapes across practically all the biogeographical regions (Bergmeier et al. 2010; Mosquera-Losada et al. 2012). Transhumance in mountain pastures and seasonal grazing under permanent-crops is still practised in many regions. In Finland, Norway and Sweden reindeer husbandry covers approximately 50 million ha, or around 35%–50% of each of these countries. Reindeer grazing could be considered as the largest agroforestry system in Europe (Holand et al. 2022; Valinger et al. 2018).

2.2 Silvoarable systems

Silvoarable systems are agroforestry practices in which trees and crops are grown simultaneously or sequentially on cropland (Nair 1993). Traditionally, these practices served as the primary source of food and resources in subsistence agriculture and were therefore widespread (Nerlich et al. 2013). In Europe, fruit or olive cultivation

with under-cropping in southern and central Europe (Streuobst, groves) and windbreaks and hedgerows in coastal regions (Bocage, Knicks) are examples of the wide variety of silvoarable agroforestry systems (Herzog 1998).

Silvoarable agroforestry in Europe can be separated into four practices (Table 1):

- **Alley cropping**, or the planting of rows of trees and/or shrubs to create alleys within which agricultural crops are produced.
- **Orchard intercropping**: including intercropped fruit trees or Streuobst (Herzog 1998), and olive orchards.
- **Alley coppice**: where species like poplar or willow are coppiced on short-rotations beneath very widely spaced timber trees. This is similar to the traditional forestry practice of coppice-with-standards, but SRC is regarded in all Member States as an agricultural land use - making alley coppice a valid form of agroforestry.
- **Agro-silvo-pasture**: where a crop is grown for part of the rotation and replaced over time by permanent grassland. In mediterranean systems with scattered evergreen oaks this period of cultivation may be crucial for the regeneration of oak seedlings.

Agriculture accounts for 41.1% of the total land area of the EU in 2018: with 24.2% arable land and 17.4% grassland. According to den Herder et al. (2017), arable agroforestry covers about 358,000 ha corresponding to about 0.2% of the total utilised agricultural area (UAA). Of this silvoarable area, 62% is in permanent crops (especially with olive trees, with 109,000 ha) and 37% is in cropland (with 130,000 ha). The most frequent combinations were (mainly oak dominated) broadleaved species with cereals and temporary grass (e.g. dehesas and montados in Portugal and Spain), and olive groves with either cereal or vegetables. There are great opportunities for use of silvoarable agroforestry on a larger scale, and with novel practices. Grass leys which have been reseeded and are less than 5-years old² are considered as "arable land", and are therefore classed as silvoarable systems.

3. LUCAS - an initial sampling approach - coming into its own for training future AI models

Reliable estimates of the extent of agroforestry are important for policy design and evaluation. This is particularly true in the case of the EU Deforestation Regulation which applies **only to forest land and not agroforestry** (CIAT & WCF 2025) and which has exposed significant errors in forest statistics even for EU Member States (Lawson, Muraru, Bertomeu, et al. 2024). Until 2009, the extent of agroforestry had not been quantified globally leading to widely varied interpretations of its importance. A first attempt to estimate the global area of agroforestry was made by (Zomer et al. 2009). In a spatial analysis using remote sensing derived global datasets, they estimated that agroforestry covers about 46% (with >10% tree cover) of the agricultural land globally. **For Europe, the authors estimated an impressive 40% (91 million ha) of agricultural land covered by agroforestry.** Later studies (Plieninger et al. 2015; den Herder et al. 2017), using a pan-European database called LUCAS (Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey) (Eurostat 2015), estimated this area at about 15.4 - 20.3 million hectares. LUCAS is a harmonized, in-situ survey conducted by Eurostat every three years. Its foundation is a systematic grid of over **1.1 million points** spaced 2 km apart, covering the entire territory of the European Union. For each campaign, a subset of these points is selected for field visits by trained surveyors. At each surveyed point, data is collected for a range of parameters, but the most critical for this analysis are Land Cover (LC) and Land Use (LU). **Land Cover** (LC) describes the biophysical coverage of the land surface (e.g., woodland, grassland, cropland, artificial surfaces). The LUCAS nomenclature for land cover is hierarchical, with 8 main categories, 29 classes, and 76 subclasses. **Land Use** (LU) describes the socio-economic purpose for which the land is used (e.g., agriculture, forestry, residential, recreation).

² The draft "2025 simplification" of the CAP ([2025/0236](#)) gives MS the opportunity to raise this limit to 7 years.

A pivotal feature of the LUCAS survey is its **double classification system for land cover**. When a surveyor encounters a multi-layered landscape, such as trees growing over a pasture, they can record both a primary land cover (LC1) and a secondary land cover (LC2). For example, a point could be coded with LC1 as "Broadleaved woodland" (C10) and LC2 as "Grassland" (E20). This capacity to capture vertical stratification is what makes LUCAS suitable for identifying agroforestry systems, which are inherently multi-layered. Furthermore, the survey records crucial Land Management parameters. For agroforestry, the most important of these is the observation of "signs of grazing". This binary indicator (present/not present) is the key filter used to distinguish silvopastoral systems from ungrazed woodlands or grasslands with trees.

Plieninger et al (2015) estimated an agroforestry area of 20.3 million hectares (using 2012 data), being much more common in the Mediterranean and Eastern Europe (Balázsi 2018). Den Herder et al. (2017) refined their methods and concluded (also using LUCAS 2012 data) that **agroforestry systems in the EU cover about 15.1 million hectares**, or 3.5% of the territorial area in the (then) EU-27³. This is about 35% of the grazed lands, or about 3.5% of the territorial area in the EU-27. Only 5.6% of the area of livestock agroforestry was within permanent crops. About half of this was in olive groves, but grazing is also important in apple- and nut-tree plantations. Silvopastoral agroforestry is most common in Spain (5.5 million ha), followed by Greece (1.6 million ha), France (1.6 million ha), Italy (1.3 million ha) and Portugal (1.1 million ha).

The process of translating a complex land use concept like agroforestry into a set of discrete database queries **reveals some limitations of the data**. The final area estimate is not a direct measurement but an inference, entirely contingent on the rules applied. For example, the decision by den Herder et al. (2017) to use a broad set of woody and grassy land covers to identify potential silvopastoral systems was driven by an ecological understanding of these landscapes. In contrast, a later methodological report by Eurostat adopted a more restrictive definition, filtering out points where the primary or secondary land use was not explicitly classified as agriculture or forestry (GOPA 2022) This seemingly minor change in the query logic had a major impact on the results, leading to a significantly smaller number of qualifying agroforestry points in the 2018 survey (3,276 points under the Eurostat definition versus 6,963 points under a definition similar to den Herder's).

This discrepancy highlights a fundamental **tension between an ecological definition (what the landscape is) and an administrative definition (how the landscape is used for official purposes)**. The broader, ecological definition used by den Herder et al. is arguably more representative of integrated systems on the ground. However, the stricter, administrative definition may be more aligned with what is considered eligible for certain agricultural subsidies under the CAP. This "methodological paradox" means that there is no single, absolute figure for the extent of agroforestry derivable from LUCAS: rather, there are different estimates that serve different purposes, one for scientific and ecological assessment and another for policy and administrative accounting. Understanding this distinction is critical for interpreting the data correctly and assessing the fitness of LUCAS for policy monitoring.

An additional methodological problem was revealed by Rubio-Delgado et al (2023). They utilized four consecutive LUCAS surveys (2009, 2012, 2015, and 2018) to investigate the temporal dynamics of agroforestry, and observed that the area of agroforestry in this period had declined by as much as 47%. In the EU-23 (the group of countries with consistent data across all four surveys) the areas fell from a predicted 19.3 Mha in 2009 to 10.3 Mha in 2018, with the great majority of the decline concentrated in silvopastoral systems. Many other studies show a decline of grazing intensity in Europe but there is little evidence of any significant abandonment of permanent pasture, at least since 2000 (Bertomeu & Lawson 2023). Machine et al (2025) suggested that much of the decline in the area of agroforestry reported by Rubio-Delgado may be due to methodological issues with LUCAS. Over the period studied, an increasing reliance on photo-interpretation rather than field visits: meaning that "signs of grazing" — such as trampled vegetation, animal tracks, or dung — increasingly go unrecorded:

³ i.e. including the UK at that time but not Croatia.

leading to under-reporting of the area of permanent grazing. Rubio-Delgado have very recently (2025) revised their estimate of the area of agroforestry in the EU in 2022 to 40.8 Mha, a great increase on previous estimates, which is largely explained by the inclusion of "small woody features" which can be derived from the LUCAS transect data. According to Rubio-Delgado et al. (2025), "small woody features" would cover the largest agroforestry area (64% of the total agroforestry area) and this type of agroforestry also saw the greatest decline (-41.9%) over 2012-2022.

Perhaps the most forward-looking application of the LUCAS dataset is its use as a **foundational "ground-truth" layer for training artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning models**. In this role, LUCAS is not the final analytical tool but rather the source of verified data used to teach algorithms how to interpret vast amounts of satellite imagery. This approach overcomes the inherent limitations of both systems: the spatial and temporal scarcity of LUCAS points and the need for calibration and validation of remote sensing data. A leading example of this synergy is the work being done by Tosh et al. within the EU-funded REFOREST project. Their research focuses on developing tools for carbon farming and biodiversity monitoring in agroforestry systems (Tosh 2025).

- **Methodology:** The researchers train **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)**, a type of deep learning model well-suited for image analysis. The models are fed approximately 40,000 high-resolution (10m) multispectral images from the Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellites.
- **Ground-Truthing:** The critical step is linking these satellite images to real, on-the-ground measurements. For this, they use data from the **LUCAS 2018 Soil Module**, which includes laboratory analysis of soil organic carbon (SOC) at thousands of points across the EU. By matching the SOC value from a LUCAS point to the satellite image of that exact location, the CNN learns to predict SOC levels based on the spectral properties of the image.
- **Output:** Once trained, these models can be applied across the entire continent to generate **high-definition, farm-scale maps of soil organic carbon and other parameters like plant biodiversity** (when trained with LUCAS and GBIF data). This allows for the creation of detailed, verifiable, and scalable monitoring systems for carbon farming initiatives in agroforestry.

Conclusion: the LUCAS land use/land cover dataset gives a sample-based insight into trends in EU agricultural land use, and is particularly valuable when linked to other datasets such as soils, biodiversity and pesticides. However, it is unlikely to provide the best estimate of EU agroforestry area or changes over time, as the wide range of published estimates shows. In the future, it is probably best used to train AI spatial models of land use and for the calibration and testing of model predictions of soil characteristics.

4. National Forest Inventories - which largely ignore Trees outside Forests (ToF)

4.1 Forest Inventories of EU Member States

National Forest Inventories (NFIs) provide the fundamental data infrastructure for forest resources across Europe. They give essential information that underpins national policy formulation, guides sustainable forest management practices, and fulfills international reporting commitments (Vidal et al. 2016). Historically, the primary objective of NFIs was to assess the productive capacity of forests, focusing predominantly on timber resources within defined forest areas (Riedel 2024). This emphasis meant that trees growing outside these conventionally delineated forest boundaries often remained unquantified or were only partially accounted for.

However, our understanding of forest ecosystems now encompasses a wider array of ecosystem services, and trees situated in non-forest environments — or "Trees Outside Forests (TOF) are increasingly valued for their contributions to environmental and societal well-being (Liu et al. 2023). These woody resources are found in diverse settings such as urban parks, agricultural hedgerows, scattered rural landscapes, and along infrastructure corridors. They play a crucial role in carbon sequestration, supporting biodiversity, regulating local climate,

influencing hydrological cycles, and providing resources for local communities. Yet, TOF remains greatly underrepresented or entirely excluded from national forest inventories. This omission results in potential biases in national carbon stock estimates and can affect the accuracy of scientific studies and climate predictions relying solely on traditional forest data (Grassi et al. 2022).

The challenge of systematically assessing TOF is compounded by their scattered nature, diverse morphological forms, and the inherent difficulties in applying conventional forest inventory methods to non-contiguous tree cover. Consistent monitoring of both forest and non-forest trees at national or regional scale is complex, and requires innovative methodologies and a harmonized data collection and reporting practices across European countries (García-Montero et al. 2021).

4.2 Defining “Trees Outside Forests (ToF)”

There are two internationally accepted definitions of Forest (Box 1)

- **FAO Definition** (used by the EU in its Deforestation Regulation) *“Forest is land spanning more than 0.5 hectares with trees higher than 5 meters and a canopy cover exceeding 10 percent, or trees capable of reaching these thresholds in situ (solid box in [Table 2](#)). Land predominantly under agricultural or urban land use is excluded”* (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2018).⁶
- **UNFCCC Definition** (used by the EU in its LULUCF Regulation) *“Forest” is a minimum area of land of 0.05-1.0 hectares with tree crown cover (or equivalent stocking level) of more than 10-30 per cent with trees with the potential to reach a minimum height of 2-5 metres at maturity in situ. A forest may consist either of closed forest formations where trees of various storeys and undergrowth cover a high proportion of the ground or open forest. Young natural stands and all plantations which have yet to reach a crown density of 10-30 per cent or tree height of 2-5 metres are included under forest, as are areas normally forming part of the forest area which are temporarily unstocked as a result of human intervention such as harvesting or natural causes but which are expected to revert to forest; [FCCC/CP/2001/13/Add.1](#)*

Member State	Area (ha)	Tree crown cover (%)	Tree height (m)	Minimum width (m)
Malta	1,0	30	5	
Spain	1,0	20	3	25
Portugal	1,0	10	5	20
Hungary	0,5	30	5	10
Estonia	0,5	30	2	
Belgium	0,5	20	5	
Netherlands	0,5	20	5	30
Denmark	0,5	10	5	20
Finland	0,5	10	5	20
France	0,5	10	5	
Italy	0,5	10	5	
Luxembourg	0,5	10	5	
Sweden	0,5	10	5	10
Greece	0,3	25	2	
Slovakia	0,3	20	5	
Cyprus	0,3	10	5	
Slovenia	0,25	30	2	
Romania	0,25	10	5	20
Lithuania	0,1	30	5	10
Ireland	0,1	20	5	20
Latvia	0,1	20	5	20
United Kingdom	0,1	20	2	20
Bulgaria	0,1	10	5	
Germany	0,1	10	5	
Croatia	0,1	10	2	
Poland	0,1	10	2	10
Austria	0,05	30	2	10
Czech Republic	0,05	30	2	20

EU Member States all have their own definitions of “Forest”, and only 3 (FR, IT, LU) fully conform to the FAO definition (Table 2).

Table 2: - threshold values used in the definitions of “forest land” in UNFCCC reports by EU Member States (Annex 2 LULUCF Regulation 2018/841). The box shows the countries whose national definition matches that used for the quinquennial FAO-Forest Resource Assessment, and proposed for all MS in the draft EU Forest Monitoring Regulation.

The FAO uses another category of "Other Wooded Land" (OWL): defined as *“land with a canopy cover of 5-10 percent of trees able to reach a height of 5 meters in situ, or a canopy cover of more than 10 percent when smaller trees, shrubs, and bushes are included”*.⁸ The Eurostat LUCAS (Land Use/Cover Area frame Survey) aligns its 'Shrubland' class this 'Other Wooded Land' category⁸ ... but there is little consistency in the OWL figures supplied by EU Member States to the FAO Forest Resource Assessment 2020 (Table 3).

"Trees Outside Forests" (TOF) are generally understood as all trees and woody vegetation that do not meet the criteria for "forest". This broad category encompasses a diverse range of tree forms and locations, including individual trees in urban settings, scattered trees on farms, linear features like hedgerows and roadside trees, and small woodlots that do not meet the minimum area or width thresholds of "forest".

Application of national definitions introduces significant variation and implications for comprehensive reporting, leading to inconsistencies in what is formally counted as "forest" or "other wooded land." For instance, the Dutch national forest surveys define forest land with a 20 percent canopy coverage, and apply this also to OWL (Anon 2020). Similarly, Ireland's forest definition for international reporting uses a minimum canopy cover of 20 percent, and forest strips must be at least 20 metres wide (Devaney et al. 2015). These national variations can result in the exclusion of significant woody biomass from core "forest" statistics, necessitating separate or complementary inventory approaches for TOF.

Table 3: Returns by EU Member States to the FAO Forest Resource Assessment 2020, showing that Trees outside Forests comprise at least 16% of the tree-covered land. However, this only looks at blocks bigger than 0.5 ha - the real area of ToF will be much larger.

Country	Forest Land ('000 ha)	Other Wooded Land ('000 ha)	Other Land with Tree Cover ('000ha)	%Trees outside Forest (OWL+OLTC)
2020 returns ('000 ha)				
Austria	3899.15	130.24	13.08	3.5%
Belgium	689.3	32.9	31.47	8.5%
Bulgaria	3893	24	13.2	0.9%
Croatia	1939.11	618.09	50	25.6%
Czechia	2677.09	0	200.25	7.0%
Cyprus	172.53	213.57	0	55.3%
Denmark	628.44	36.95	2.67	5.9%
Estonia	2438.4	94.44	3.6	3.9%
Finland	22409	746	9	3.3%
France	17253	843	206	5.7%
Germany	11419	0	400	3.4%
Greece	3901.8	2634.72	1000	48.2%
Hungary	2053.01	200	82.24	12.1%
Ireland	782.02	65.74	0.67	7.8%
Italy	9566.13	1865.84	2718.37	32.4%
Latvia	3410.79	107.8	182.61	7.8%
Lithuania	2201	62.1	19.5	3.6%
Luxembourg	88.7	2.7	0	3.0%
Malta	0.46	0.07	4.7	91.2%
Netherlands	369.5	0	21.55	5.5%
Poland	9483	0	0	0.0%
Portugal	3312	1543	0	31.8%
Romania	6929.05	15.57	0	0.2%
Slovakia	1925.9	20.41	0	1.0%
Slovenia	1237.83	27.42	288	20.3%
Spain	18572.17	9381.82	3902.36	41.7%
Sweden	27980	2364	0	7.8%
Total	159231.4	21030.4	9149.3	15.9%
Switzerland	1269.11	74.92	301.69	22.9%
United Kingdom	3190	20	24	1.4%

This definitional bottleneck is a primary reason why a "standardised" forest definition, such as suggested in the Forest Monitoring Regulation is unrealistic and counter productive (Lawson 2023a). According to this reference (EURAF Policy Briefing #15) trees outside forests are very much under-reported in both EU and FAO statistics. The need for accurate reporting of GHG emissions from "grassland" and "cropland" for LULUCF and carbon farming purposes may provide the spur needed for improved TOF reporting. This would require clear national forest definitions and reliable rural-cadastrs, to distinguish forest land from agricultural land. It does not require a unified definition of "forest" to be applied across Europe. Forcing MS to have a single definition (e.g. in the draft Forest Monitoring Regulation) will hinder accurate GHG reporting by perpetuating confusion on the boundary between forestry and agriculture (Table 3).

4.4 Differences between Member States in reporting of Trees Outside Forests in National Forest Inventories

Reporting of TOF in NFIs is characterized by a spectrum of approaches, ranging from explicit, dedicated inventories to implicit inclusion within broader land-use classifications. While the fundamental definitions of "forest" often exclude trees in agricultural or urban settings, several countries have recognized the ecological and carbon sequestration importance of these non-forest woody resources and have adapted their monitoring systems accordingly. Table 4 provides an overview of how selected European countries address TOF and Other Wooded Land (OWL) in their national forest inventories or through complementary assessment systems.

Table 4: European Countries with Explicit TOF/OWL Reporting in National Forest Inventories.

Country	Explicit TOF/OWL Inclusion in NFI/Complementary Systems (Yes/No/Partial)	Key TOF Categories/Definitions	Primary Assessment Methods	Estimated TOF Contribution ³	Noteworthy Contributions/Challenges
United Kingdom	Yes (via dedicated TOW map integrated with NFI)	Trees Outside Woodland (TOW): lone trees, groups of trees, small woodlands, hedges (>0.5m height planned) outside NFI woodland definition (>0.5ha) ¹⁴	Satellite imagery (Sentinel-2), airborne LiDAR, spatial algorithms, expert calibration, field surveys ¹⁴	22.1% of total tree cover, 9.9% of total tree biomass (for England) ³	Pioneering dedicated, high-resolution TOW mapping to complement NFI; strong institutional link for LULUCF reporting. ¹⁶ Addresses historical NFI gap where 30% of tree cover was unmapped. ¹⁴
Netherlands	Partial/Limited (OWL not formally registered in NBI)	"Other plantings (landscape, avenues, wooded banks etc)" implicitly captured if meeting forest criteria. ²⁰ Research identifies urban and agricultural trees. ³	NBI: Systematic sampling grid for forest inventory. ²¹ Research: Nanosatellite imagery, airborne LiDAR. ³	24.6% of total tree cover, 12.2% of total tree biomass. Urban trees contribute 8% of national carbon stocks. ³	Explicitly states OWL is not registered as per FAO definition within NBI. ¹² National forest definition (20% canopy cover) is stricter than FAO's. ¹²
Ireland	Partial (NFI assesses "forest estate" with stricter definition; TOF biomass quantified by research)	Forest definition for international reporting (≥20% canopy cover). ¹³ Research identifies trees outside forests. ³	NFI: Randomized systematic grid sample plots. ²² Remote sensing (SAR, machine learning) for forest cover estimation. ¹³	19.7% of total tree cover, 8.8% of total tree biomass ³	National forest definition is stricter than FAO's, potentially limiting explicit OWL/TOF inclusion within core NFI. ¹³ Research highlights significant TOF presence.
Denmark	Partial (TOF recognized for afforestation/biomass; not distinct NFI category)	Urban forests, trees for groundwater protection and recreation (as part of afforestation). ²³ Specific risk assessment for TOF biomass. ²⁴	NFI: Sample-based for growing stock. ²⁵ Research: Satellite imagery, AI, NFI data for calibration. ¹⁷	19.5% of total tree cover, 7.5% of total tree biomass ³	TOF are acknowledged as drivers of forest area increase and for specific policy objectives, but generally "not currently counted in national forest inventories" as distinct TOF. ¹⁷

France	Yes (via dedicated "lignieux hors forêt" inventory)	Lignieux hors forêt: hedges (haies), scattered trees (arbres épars), orchard meadows (prés-vergers), orchards (vergers), alignements ²⁶	Annual field surveys (including hedgerows), photointerpretation mapping (GIS, orthophotos), coordination with Teruti Land Use Study ¹¹	9.7% of total tree cover, 3.2% of total tree biomass ³	Explicit, operational, and generalizing inventory for various TOF categories. Active efforts to harmonize TOF data with broader land-use studies. ¹¹
Germany	Partial/Implicit (data collected, but not explicit TOF category)	Non-tree backgrounds in remote sensing data; non-forest related measures in LULUCF accounting. ³⁰	NFI: Systematic sampling grid, field measurements, integration of remote sensing data for higher spatial resolution. ³⁰	10.0% of total tree cover, 2.9% of total tree biomass ³	Comprehensive NFI with broad land-use data collection and remote sensing, but TOF are likely derived or implicitly accounted for rather than explicitly inventoried as a distinct category. ³⁰
Estonia	Yes (explicitly covers OWL and non-forest land)	Other Wooded Land (OWL) and non-forest land growing stock. ³³	NFI: Systematic sampling grid, circular sample plots, integration of satellite data (optical, SAR) and airborne LiDAR with NFI data and machine learning. ³³	3.0% of total tree cover, 1.0% of total tree biomass ³	Comprehensive NFI covering all land use classes; explicit classification of OWL on measured sample plots since 2005, aligning with FRA standards. ³³
Finland	Partial/Implicit (NFI covers broad categories, but detailed TOF reporting less emphasized)	Poorly productive forest land and unproductive land (categories that may contain TOF). ³⁵	Multi-source NFI: Field data, satellite images (LANDSAT, ALOS), digital map data. ³⁷	1.7% of total tree cover, 0.6% of total tree biomass ³	High forest cover reduces perceived need for distinct TOF inventory. Detailed metrics like tree growth are primarily focused on traditional "forest" areas. ³⁸
Italy	Yes (focus on spatial characterization of TOF)	Homogeneous areas (500-5000 m ²), elongated features (3-20m width), forest patches, isolated trees, tree hedgerows. ³⁹	Detailed photointerpretation mapping (GIS, high-resolution orthophotos), automated methods using optical data (Sentinel-2). ³⁹	7.5% of total tree cover, 2.5% of total tree biomass ³	Explicit focus on spatial characterization of TOF at the national level. Acknowledges need for less traditional sampling schemes for TOF. ³⁹

Member States fall into 3 categories relating to their NFI reporting of Trees outside Forests: a) explicit reporting, b) partial or implicit reporting and c) very little reporting

4.4.1 EXPLICIT REPORTING OF TOF/OWL

United Kingdom: The UK stands out for its proactive and explicit inventories of Trees Outside Forest, which it prefers to call Trees outside Woodland (TOW). The UK Government initiated a dedicated mapping of TOW in England (NCEA 2025), aiming to give a comprehensive picture of all tree canopy in England outside the National Forest Inventory map of forests >.5ha (Anon n.d.) and the existing map of "small woodlands (0.1-0.5ha) (Brewer, A., Ditchburn, B., Cross, D., Whitton, E., Ward, A. 2017). The methodology for TOW mapping is highly advanced, relying on satellite imagery (Sentinel-2) and airborne LiDAR data, processed through sophisticated spatial algorithms and calibrated with expert input. This enables the identification and mapping of diverse TOF features, including lone trees, small tree groups, and small woodlands that typically fall below the NFI's minimum area thresholds. The importance of this comprehensive assessment is underscored by the significant contribution of TOF to national carbon stocks, biodiversity, and natural capital (Forest Research 2022). Furthermore, the institutional alignment between the NFI, TOW mapping, and the UK's Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) greenhouse gas inventory ensures that these non-forest woody resources are systematically accounted for in international climate reporting, particularly under "Settlements", "Grassland" and "Cropland" categories (Brown et al. 2025)

France: France demonstrates a long-standing commitment to assessing woody vegetation beyond conventional forest boundaries through its *Inventaire des ligneux hors forêt* (Bélouard & Coulon 2001). This dedicated inventory, managed by the National Institute of Geographic and Forest Information (IGN), is operational and is being progressively generalized across the entire French territory. The French system explicitly defines and inventories various TOF categories, including hedges ("haies"), scattered trees ("arbres épars"), orchard meadows ("prés-vergers"), and orchards ("vergers"), as well as alignments of trees. While the core "Forêt" definition in France, consistent with FAO guidelines, explicitly excludes agricultural land like orchards, other land cover classifications within the NFI, such as "Autre végétation" (other vegetation), specifically include orchards and nurseries (IGN 2019). The methodology involves detailed field surveys, where inventory teams visit points located not only in forests but also in a copse, heathland or close to a hedgerow. It is visited by a team of two field staff who record the dendrometric, floristic, pedological features and other variables. They also observe and measure the trees (species, circumference, height, growth, health, etc.), and describe the forest stand, lying deadwood, vegetation, regeneration and pressure from large ungulates, as well as the ecological conditions (slope, exposure and soil) (IGN 2025). Efforts are also underway to coordinate these TOF classifications with the annual Teruti Land Use Study with the ultimate goal of updating NFI data using a unified national nomenclature (CASD 2015). This systematic and detailed approach to TOF assessment makes France a notable example of comprehensive non-forest tree reporting in Europe.

Italy: Italy has explicitly focused on the spatial characterization of Trees Outside Forests (TOFs) at the national level within its National Forest Inventory framework (Ottaviano & Marchetti 2023). This recognition stems from the understanding that TOFs are vital components of green infrastructure and agroforestry systems. The Italian NFI defines TOFs with specific spatial criteria: a homogeneous area of land use and cover between 500 and 5000 square meters, or, if elongated, with a width between 3 and 20 meters. This allows for the classification of various TOF structures, including small forest patches, isolated trees, and tree hedgerows (Sarti et al. 2021). The methodology for assessing these features combines traditional detailed photointerpretation mapping using GIS and high-resolution orthophotos with automated methods based on optical data from Sentinel-2 satellites. While acknowledging that sampling protocols designed for traditional forests may not be optimal for scattered TOF, and that "less traditional sampling schemes" may be needed, Italy's explicit focus on TOF characterization demonstrates a commitment to capturing these important resources.

Estonia: Estonia's National Forest Inventory (NFI) stands out for its comprehensive scope, which explicitly covers "all land use classes, including all forests and other wooded lands in all ownership groups" (FAO 2020). This broad mandate ensures that woody vegetation beyond strict forest definitions is systematically inventoried. The Estonian NFI provides information on the distribution of land by land-use classes and the growing stock on "non-forest land". Critically, since 2005, the NFI has consistently assigned FAO "forest" and "Other Wooded Land" (OWL) classifications to every measured sample plot, thereby aligning its national data with international reporting standards.³³ The methodology is robust, employing a systematic sampling design across the entire country, supported by the integration of advanced remote sensing technologies such as satellite data (optical, Synthetic Aperture Radar) and airborne laser scanning (LiDAR) with NFI field data and machine learning techniques. This comprehensive approach ensures that Estonia's NFI effectively captures and reports on a wide range of woody vegetation, including OWL and other non-forest tree resources. (Omoniyi & Sims 2024)

4.5.2 COUNTRIES WITH PARTIAL OR IMPLICIT TOF/OWL REPORTING

Netherlands: The Netherlands presents a more nuanced picture regarding TOF reporting. While a significant percentage of its total tree cover (24.6%) and biomass (12.2%) is estimated to exist outside forests, particularly in urban areas (8% of national carbon stocks- (Liu et al. 2023)), the Dutch National Forest Inventory (NFI) does not formally register "other wooded land" as per the FAO definition. The NFI primarily focuses on the biomass and wood production aspects of its defined forest areas (Lerink 2014). Although the NFI's results are used for international reporting obligations like the FAO Forest Resource Assessment and Forest Europe, this explicit non-registration of OWL within the national framework represents a notable data gap. Furthermore, the national forest definition used in the Netherlands employs a stricter 20% canopy coverage threshold compared to FAO's 10% (Anon 2020), potentially leading to the exclusion of some sparse woody areas from their "forest" classification. While the NFI does mention "Other plantings (landscape, avenues, wooded banks etc)" as a small percentage of forest area (9%) (Anon 2022), this does not fully capture the breadth of TOF. The quantification of TOF biomass in the Netherlands has largely been driven by external research utilizing high-resolution remote sensing, highlighting a disconnect between academic assessment and formal NFI inclusion.

Ireland: Ireland's National Forest Inventory (NFI) conducts detailed periodic surveys of its "entire national forest estate," collecting multi-resource information including forest area, species composition, growing stock, biodiversity, and carbon content (DAFM 2022). However, for international reporting, Ireland applies a forest definition with a minimum canopy cover of 20%, which is more stringent than the FAO's 10% threshold. This stricter definition may implicitly exclude certain areas that would qualify as OWL or sparse forest under broader international guidelines. Despite this, external studies have quantified a notable proportion of Ireland's total tree cover (19.7%) and biomass (8.8%) as existing outside forests (Liu et al. 2023). The NFI does utilize remote sensing technologies, such as Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) and machine learning algorithms, for forest cover estimation (Devaney et al. 2015). While the NFI aims for comprehensive assessment of its forest resources, explicit, separate reporting on TOF categories beyond what meets the national forest definition is not clearly detailed in the available information, suggesting that TOF data might be derived or addressed through broader land-use categories rather than a dedicated inventory.

Denmark: Denmark's approach to TOF reporting is characterized by a partial and somewhat implicit inclusion within its NFI and related policy frameworks. The Danish National Forest Inventory (NFI) serves as the primary source for growing stock data and contributes to LULUCF CO₂ emissions/removals reporting to the UNFCCC. Notably, afforestation efforts in Denmark have significantly increased forest area, with "urban forests, groundwater protection and recreation" identified as key drivers (Bo Larsen et al. n.d.).²³ This indicates that trees in these non-traditional forest settings can be recognized and accounted for when they contribute to the overall forest area, however work by Liu et al at the University of Copenhagen confirms that almost 20% of tree crown cover in Denmark may be outside forests (Table 5)

Table 5: Country statistics of tree cover and biomass
(Anon 2023)

Country statistics of tree cover and biomass:				
Country	Total tree cover (% of country)	Tree cover outside forests (% of total)	Total biomass in Tg	Tree biomass outside forests in Tg (% of total)
Ireland	10.5%	19.7%	36.65	3.24 (8.8%)
United Kingdom	14.1%	22.1%	264.29	26.29 (9.9%)
The Netherlands	14.8%	24.6%	47.32	5.79 (12.2%)
Denmark	16.9%	19.5%	63.47	4.74 (7.5%)
Ukraine	20.1%	11.4%	1534.2	53.2 (3.5%)
France	34.6%	9.7%	2388.2	77.2 (3.2%)
Germany	36.1%	10.0%	2264.3	65.4 (2.9%)
Italy	38.6%	7.5%	1501.3	37.6 (2.5%)
Estonia	50.3%	3.0%	259.3	2.7 (1.0%)
Finland	67.8%	1.7%	1726.2	9.76 (0.6%)

This suggests that while TOF are acknowledged for their role in landscape greening and carbon sequestration, they are not a distinct, comprehensively inventoried category within the core NFI. Nevertheless, Denmark's Sustainable Biomass Program (SBP) includes a specific "Regional Risk Assessment for Denmark - Trees Outside Forests" (Anon 2024b), indicating a policy-driven assessment of TOF for biomass sourcing, which represents a form of TOF reporting driven by specific economic and environmental objectives.

Germany: The German National Forest Inventory (BWI) is a robust and systematic sampling-based inventory that covers the entire country and collects extensive data on forest resources.² While the BWI's primary focus remains on traditional forest attributes such as forest area, growing stock, and timber increment (Riedel 2023), it contributes essential data for international reporting obligations, including the Kyoto Protocol and UNFCCC. The German NFI integrates remote sensing data, which includes analysis of "non-tree backgrounds" in its datasets, suggesting an awareness of woody vegetation beyond strict forest boundaries (Freudenberg et al. 2025).³⁰ Furthermore, Germany accounts for "non-forest related measures" in its LULUCF sector for carbon sink projections (Wirth et al. 2024). This indicates that while Germany does not have a dedicated, explicit inventory for "trees outside forests" as a distinct category, data relevant to TOF is likely collected or derived implicitly through its comprehensive land-use classifications and remote sensing analyses, particularly for climate change mitigation accounting.

Finland: Finland, a country with very high forest cover, employs a multi-source National Forest Inventory (NFI) approach through the Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke) (Tomppo 2000). The NFI systematically samples the "total land and inland water area" and produces raster maps that cover "forest land, poorly productive forest land and unproductive land" (Anon 2021). The categories of "poorly productive forest land" and "unproductive land" likely encompass some forms of TOF or sparse woody vegetation that do not meet the full criteria for "forest." The Finnish NFI integrates field data with satellite imagery and other digital map data to generate estimates and thematic maps. However, for detailed analyses such as annual tree growth evaluation, the focus remains primarily on "locations with land-cover classified as forest" (Anon 2025) This suggests that while woody vegetation outside core forests might be identified through broad land classification, it may not be subject to the same level of detailed inventory or explicit reporting as a distinct TOF category, possibly due to the relatively low proportion of TOF compared to Finland's extensive forest cover.

4.6 Harmonization Efforts and Remaining Challenges

The diverse approaches to TOF reporting across European countries highlight the persistent challenges in achieving comprehensive and comparable pan-European data. International and regional bodies have long recognized the need for harmonization to facilitate consistent reporting for global agreements and regional policies.

4.6.1 INTERNATIONAL HARMONIZATION INITIATIVES

The European National Forest Inventory Network (ENFIN) plays a pivotal role in promoting and harmonizing forest inventory information across Europe. Comprising 34 members from 31 European countries, ENFIN serves as a

platform for experienced NFI specialists to collaborate on harmonizing forest data (Anon 2024a).⁴⁶ A core objective of ENFIN is to "provide a platform for the harmonisation of forest inventory information at European scale" and to "bridge gaps between national and reference definitions" This directly addresses the definitional inconsistencies that complicate TOF reporting. ENFIN's efforts contribute to supporting forest policies with harmonized information and adapting data collection to new emerging policy needs.

COST Actions, such as E43 "Harmonisation of National Inventories in Europe: Techniques for Common Reporting" and FP1001/USEWOOD "Improving Data and Information on the Potential Supply of Wood Resources: A European Approach from Multisource National Forest Inventories", have been instrumental in these harmonization efforts. COST Action E43, involving 27 European countries and the US, aimed to improve and harmonize existing NFIs by developing "reference definitions" and "methods called bridges" to adjust national estimates to these common standards (Winter et al. 2008). COST Action FP1001/USEWOOD explicitly identified "trees outside the forest" as a major issue to be clarified for understanding the potential supply of tree biomass (Anon 2010). These initiatives underscore the long-standing recognition of the need for harmonized TOF data, particularly for assessing wood resources and carbon pools.

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) also play central roles in collecting, validating, and disseminating harmonized forest statistics for the UNECE region, including Europe.⁶ Their joint efforts, such as the Global Forest Resources Assessments (FRA) and the "State of Europe's Forests" (SoEF) reports, rely on country reports and remote sensing data. The SoEF 2020 report, for instance, includes "growing stock on forest and other wooded land" (Forest Europe 2015).

4.6.2 PERSISTENT CHALLENGES AND DATA GAPS

Despite these harmonization efforts, several challenges continue to impede comprehensive and comparable TOF reporting across Europe.

One primary challenge is the aforementioned definitional inconsistencies.¹ While international definitions exist, national interpretations and adaptations lead to variations in what constitutes "forest," "other wooded land," or "trees outside forests." This is evident in the Netherlands' explicit non-registration of OWL as per FAO definitions, or Ireland's stricter canopy cover threshold for forest definition. These national specificities make direct comparisons of TOF data difficult without complex "bridging functions" (Winter et al. 2008).⁴⁹

Another significant issue is the completeness and detail of data collection for TOF. While some countries like France and the UK have dedicated, detailed inventories for TOF categories¹⁴, the "State of Europe's Forests 2020" report explicitly notes that "in many countries, the growing stock data are missing for OWL" and that the attributed growing stock for OWL is "very low as a rule" due to definitional thresholds that exclude smaller trees and shrubs common in OWL (Forest Europe 2015) This indicates that even when OWL is conceptually included, its quantitative assessment is often incomplete or limited.

Data timeliness and accessibility also pose challenges. National forest inventories are typically updated every 5-10 years, which means they can quickly become outdated, especially in dynamic landscapes.⁵³ This impacts the accuracy of TOF data, which can change rapidly due to land-use shifts or small-scale removals. Recent discussions around the European Parliament's draft Forest Monitoring Regulation have raised concerns about a potential weakening of provisions related to Earth Observation, data precision, and a shift towards voluntary data-sharing among Member States, which could further hinder the availability of consistent, real-time TOF information (FERN 2025)

Finally, the integration of TOF data into broader national and international reporting frameworks remains a work in progress. While some countries, like the UK, are actively merging dedicated TOF data with NFI data for a "complete picture"¹⁶, and others implicitly account for TOF in LULUCF reporting (e.g., Germany's "non-forest

related measures" ³¹), a fully unified and transparent system across all European countries for all TOF attributes is yet to be realized. The challenge lies not just in collecting the data, but in consistently integrating it into established reporting mechanisms that have historically focused on traditional forest definitions.

4.6.3 THE ENABLING ROLE OF REMOTE SENSING

Technological advancements, particularly in remote sensing, are proving crucial in overcoming some of the traditional limitations in TOF assessment. High-resolution satellite imagery (e.g., 3-meter nanosatellite imagery, Sentinel-2) and airborne laser scanning (LiDAR) enable the accurate mapping and quantification of tree cover and biomass, including scattered trees that are often missed by traditional field methods or lower-resolution imagery (Liu et al. 2023). Countries like the UK, Italy, and Estonia are actively integrating these technologies into their national assessment systems to capture TOF more effectively. This technological capability offers a promising pathway towards more comprehensive and spatially explicit TOF inventories across Europe, providing data that can be used to enhance estimates for key forest resource parameters (Barrett et al. 2016).

Conclusion⁴: assessment of Trees Outside Forests (TOF) in European National Forest Inventories (NFIs) is complex. While the traditional definitions of "forest" often exclude trees in agricultural and urban landscapes, there is growing recognition of the significant ecological, economic, and climate-related contributions of these non-forest woody resources. This recognition is increasingly driven by international climate agreements and European environmental policies that necessitate a more comprehensive accounting of all tree cover and associated carbon stocks. It is noted that the draft EU Forest Monitoring Regulation does not mention the importance of Trees outside Forests.

5. CAP IACS Geospatial Systems - the elusive "holy grail"

EURAF Policy Briefing #68 (v1) gives approaches to the quantification of agroforestry and woody landscape features in the EU using Member States' Geospatial Aid Application (GSAA) and Land Parcel Information System (LPIS) data (Lawson et al. 2025). All Member States (MS) maintain a CAP Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS). This has several components. One is a national or regional Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) (Zysk et al. 2020; Cetl et al. 2023) which locates all eligible agricultural land within reference parcels and calculates their maximum eligible area (MEA). Another is the Geo-Spatial Aid Application (GSAA) which contains farmers declarations on the boundaries of eligible parcels (and sub-parcels), what they are cultivating, and animals involved⁵. Farmers declare their "agricultural parcels" in relation to the established LPIS "reference parcels".

Only in a few countries, such as Spain, is the LPIS system integrated with national forest inventories (NFI) and used for Land Use Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) reporting as part of national inventories of Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions. The LPIS is therefore not yet a comprehensive land use system. It also fails to record reference parcels for holdings which do not meet the minimum size threshold for "active farmers", or where "hobby farmers" do not choose to apply for area payments. Member States (European Commission 2023a) apply minimum payment thresholds (ranging between €100 and €500) and/or minimum holding areas (ranging from 0.3 ha to 4 ha) to decide on the definition of "active farmers". Areas of woodland on farms may be recorded in LPIS systems, but usually only for parcels which have received an afforestation grant or a forest environment payment.

Land-use maps are complex and reflect differences in legislation, regulation and survey practices between jurisdictions. The objectives of land-use and cadastral systems tend to be the same however (Grant et al. 2020).

⁴ During the preparation of Chapter 4 the authors used Gemini Deep Research to retrieve information which would otherwise have been difficult to obtain. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and they take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

⁵ In Ireland the "Herd Number" is used to identify farm holdings and a unique number is used even for arable farms. It is not yet apparent which MS provide a unique identifier, such as this, for holdings in their public LPIS systems.

Recently, the United Nations Committee of Experts on Global Geospatial Information Management (UN-GGIM) adopted the Framework for Effective Land Administration (FELA) (UN-GGIM 2020). This could be an ideal moment for the GSAA-LPIS to be harmonised as an **Integrated Rural Land Parcel Registry**, and linked to other initiatives like the European Land Information Service (European Commission n.d.).

The DigitAF project is building on the core conceptual model of the LPIS (Sagris et al. 2013; Sagris & Devos 2008; Inan et al. 2010) to provide parcel boundary, land use and crop data to our agroforestry modelling teams. This follows other attempts to harmonise the LPIS (Skokanová et al. 2020; Krumsteds et al. 2019; Campos-Taberner et al. 2019; Černecký et al. 2020; Dobosz et al. 2019; Campos-Taberner et al. 2023; Špulerová et al. 2022; Delgado Hernández & Valcárcel Sanz 2022; JRC 2023). In particular, the JRC report on "*Geodata and technologies for a greener agriculture in Europe*" (JRC 2023) has highlighted possibilities for new techniques to capture areas of peatland, landscape features and agroforestry from the detailed orthophotos available in LPIS Systems.

Figure 1: Categories of LPIS systems in the EU (Sagris & Devos 2008; Wiemann et al. 2013).

LPIS systems in Member States fall into four categories (Figure 1). MS with *Agricultural Parcels* and *Farmers Blocks* hold little information about forests (other than areas aided by afforestation and rural development programmes), whereas MS with *Physical Blocks* and *Cadastral Parcels* **may** contain forest information. However, availability of this data varies from country to country, and a thorough review is required of inclusion of forestry, agroforestry and landscape feature geospatial information in the LPIS of all Member States, together with assessment of actions needed for each MS to: a) fully integrate GIS systems for forestry and agriculture, and b) undertake further reconciliation with their national cadastres (including land ownership information).

Technical Guidance on LPIS data discovery (Toth & Milenov 2020) and data sharing (Martirano & Toth 2023) is available from the EU Joint Research Centre, and use of the GSAA-LPIS is stressed in a very recent Commission Notice (C/2025/980) *Guidance on a framework for developing methodologies to monitor high-diversity of landscape features pursuant to Article 14(7) of the Nature Restoration Regulation (2024/1991)*

Information on Landscape features as declared in Member States is given in EURAF Policy Briefing #21 (Table 6). All Member States except Finland, Sweden and Malta recognise some form of woody landscape feature, although there are only 19 which identify isolated trees. Countries vary greatly in how these features are recorded in their IACS systems, and this will be the object of further study by the DigitAF Project.

There are also discrepancies between the maximum size of agricultural woody landscape features declared in CAP Strategic Plans and the minimum dimensions declared for forests in national legislation (shown in red in Table 5). This may cause confusion in some Member States.

Table 6: Dimensions and breakdown of landscape features declared by Member States in CAP Statistics (Lawson & de Boeck 2023)

CAP-M	Landscape feature and non productive area	AT	BEF	BEW	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL	ES	FI	FR	HU	HR	IE	IT	LT	LU	LV	MT	NL	PL	PT	RO	SE	SK	SI	Sum	
B151	Fallow Land	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1		2		2	1	2		3				30	
B152	Hedges or woody strips	1	1	1	1			1		1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1		1	1	1		1	1	20	
B152	Trees in Line		1	1	1		1	1		1	1	1		1		1	1	1		1	1		1	2	1	1		1	1	21	
B152	Trees in Groups/ Copses	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1		1	1	1	1		1	2	1	1		1	1	24	
B152	Isolated Trees			1	1	1	1	1			1	1		1	1	1		1	1	1	1		1		1	1		1	1	19	
B153	Buffer Strips	1	1	1	1			1									1	1			1	1	1			1		1	1	13	
B153	Field Margins (# types)		1	3	1	2	7	1	1	1		1		1	2		7	1	1	4	1		4		1	1	2	1		44	
B153	Forest Edge Strips - non prod		1	1	1					1		1				1	1													7	
B154	Ditches			1			1			1	1			1		1	1	1	1		1		3	1	1	1				16	
B154	Streams										1											1	1							3	
B155	Small Ponds	1	1	1							1	1		1	1		1	1	1	1		1	1		1				1	15	
B155	Small Wetlands					1	1				1									1	1	1	1	1						8	
B156	Traditional Stone Walls	1						1		1	1	1		1		1	1	1			1	1							1	12	
B157	Cairns	1						1			1	1							1	1	1					1				8	
B158	Terraces					1	1				1	1			1			1				1							y	7	
B159	Cultural Features	1		5					1	1	1	1			1		1							1						13	
B160	Others			1		2	1	1			2							1	1				4	1	1			-		15	
B161	Cover or catch crops (7% option)		-	-		1		-	-	-	-			1	1				-				-		-					3	
B162	N-Fixing Crops (7% option)		-	-		1				1	-	-		1	1				-				-		-			-		4	
	Total elements / sub-elements active	8	8	19	8	4	18	11	6	11	13	14	1	11	12	8	16	12	8	11	11	6	21	9	10	8	5	6	7	282	
	4% Option	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	28
	3% Option	y		y	y			y	y	y	y				y				y	y			y		y					12	
	7% Option		y	y	y	y	y			y	y	y		y	y				y				y	y	y	y		y		16	
	LULUCF Regulation - threshold of "forest land" (ha)	0.05	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.05	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.3	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	1	0.5	0.1	1	0.25	0.5	0.3	0.25		
	Strategic Plan - max LF copse/grove size (ha)	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	-	?	0.2	?	?	?	0.3	-	0.5	0.5	?	-	0.3		0.3	0.5	-	1.5	0.5	0.5	0.9	-	?	0.5		
	Details of hedge width and permitted gaps?	y	y	y	y			y		y		y		y	y	y		y	y	y			y			y				15	
	Details of permitted crown size of trees in line?		y	y	y					y				y		y		y		y			y	y	y	y			y	13	
	Details of crown size of isolated trees?			y	y										y	y		y					y	y					y	8	
RED shows where the definition of "copse/grove" on agricultural land differs from the national definition the minimum size threshold for a forest block. In many countries the size threshold is not given or copses/groves are not recognised as Landscape Features																															

Landscape Features are recorded in CAP Result Indicator 34 (European Commission 2023b)- "Share of UAA under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees % (Table 7), but MS vary considerably in the way this is reported, with some countries including including payments for establishment of permanent crops like vineyards or olives.

Table 7: Planned area of CAP Result Indicator 34 "Share of UAA under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees (%)" Note that R.34 measures the share of overall UAA, not just arable land.

Member State	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	Change
Austria	7.5	7.7	8.3	8.3	8.1	"++"
Belgium-Flanders	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0
Belgium-Wallonia	<0.5	1.6	1.9	2.1	2.4	"++"
Bulgaria	1.1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	"??"
Croatia	0.5	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	"+"
Cyprus	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	0
Czechia	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0
Denmark	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9	0
Estonia	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Finland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0
France	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Germany	3.0	3.6	3.9	4.0	4.2	"++"
Greece	13.8	13.3	14.8	14.8	16.8	"++"
Hungary	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Ireland	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.7	0
Italy	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Latvia	0.0	0.0	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	"+"
Lithuania	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	0
Luxembourg	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	0
Malta	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0
Netherlands	3.0	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6	"+"
Poland	<0.5	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	"++"
Portugal	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Romania	0.0	2.1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	"??"
Slovakia	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.3	"++"
Slovenia	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.6	"+"
Spain	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Sweden	0.0	0.0	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	"+"

Fire management plans are another application for detailed mapping. Goats, sheep, cattle, horses and pigs can be introduced carefully into fire-breaks or thinned sub-parcels in established forests, and managed in a way to reduce the volume of dead branches and shrubs on the forest floor (Bertomeu et al. 2022; Lasanta et al. 2018). This greatly decreases the intensity and risk of propagation of fires. Access to a fully integrated land use system (LPIS) that shows both forest parcels and nearby agricultural parcels with tree-cover (e.g. parkland, Dehesa and Montado) would greatly facilitate the planning of fire response and grazing agreements with local shepherds.

Four Member States (BE-F, FI, IT, CY) do not have any eco-schemes mapped against Result Indicator 34 (share of UAA under supported commitments to maintain landscape features) in the Catalogue of CAP Interventions, and only six MS have eco-schemes which specifically mention "landscape" in their titles. The creation of new landscape feature eco-schemes on arable land (as promised in the Simplification Regulation 2024/1469 - as a replacement for GAEC8) has therefore not happened in many Member States. Further data on this is awaited from DGAGRI. EURAF and ELO also plan to update Policy Briefing 22 (Lawson & de Boeck 2023), which recorded the dimensions of landscape features, and the way that they were mapped in GSAA-LPIS systems. Lawson & Muraru (2025) give more details on landscape feature support in the CAP and the "carrot" v "stick" argument for GAEC 8.

The following rules to prioritise the determination of land-use are proposed for further work in the DigitAF LPIS Sustainability Compass (Deliverable 1.4).

1. LPIS parcels classed as "cropland" or "grassland" are tagged as "silvoarable" or "silvopastoral" if Copernicus Tree Cover Density (%TCD) =>5%⁶
2. LPIS parcels classed as "agriculture" remain so irrespective of NFI or JRC "forest" designations

⁶ The figure of 5% TCD is recommended since this is the minimum cover threshold used in the FAO Forest Resource Assessment for the category Other Wooded Land (FAO 2002; FAO 2010)

3. LPIS parcels classed as "forest" remain so irrespective of NFI or JRC "forest" designations.
4. Land with no LPIS parcel present is classed as "cropland", "grassland" or "forest" depending on Copernicus and JRC 10m raster information.
5. "Settlement", "wetland" and "other" land is derived from the Corine LCS+ 100m dataset.

Following UNFCCC-LULUCF rules, land parcels can be either forest, cropland (arable and permanent crops), grassland, wetland, settlement or other. **There can be no overlap or ambiguity.** Agroforestry parcels are found on cropland and grassland. Wetland, settlement and forest agroforestry are not currently considered.

5.1 Availability of GSAA and IACS Data

The EU INSPIRE Directive, obliges Member States to make geospatial data collected with public funds available in their national INSPIRE portals (link). Manual inspection of the Member States making LPIS datasets available through these portals improved significantly in 2024, but there were still 11 countries which do not meet this open data requirement for LPIS data in their INSPIRE Portals, and 11 (often different) which do not provide LPIS data through the DGAGRI agro-food geoportal (link). In total, 19 administrations from 28 provide online endpoints to harvest GSAA and LPIS data.⁷ However it is not sufficient to provide access to datafiles through the INSPIRE or DGAGRI portals. More demanding criteria are stipulated in the **High Value Datasets Regulation (2023/138)**.

An AI assisted review was therefore undertaken of the MS which met the six criteria for compliance with the HVD Regulation i.e.: free of charge, full-open reuse licence, machine readable format, API access, bulk download, up to date (Table 8). Only two countries were **“Fully Compliant”** (AT, LU), while 13 were **“Largely Compliant”** (BE-W, CZ, DK, EE, FI, FR, IE, LV, NL, PT, SK, SL, SE), 1 was **“Largely Compliant but Fragmented”** (ES), 6 were **“Partially Compliant”** (BE-F, HR, CY, LT, MT, PL), 2 were **“Highly Fragmented and Partially Compliant”** (DE, IT), and 4 were **“Non-Compliant”** (BG, EL, HU, RO).

5.2 Availability of LPIS crop and land use codes

DigitAF is maintaining a list here of crop codes, land-use codes, and meta-references used in Member States. The LAMASUS Project and other Horizon projects are helping the EuroCrops project to maintain a GitHub list of national crop codes and their mapping through the common HCAT3 code. This has crop codes have been added for AT, BE-F, BE_W, CZ, DE (BB, IS, NRW), DK, EE, ES, FI, FR, HR, IE, LT, LV, NL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK (19)

Missing countries in HCAT3 are therefore BG, CY, EL, HU, IT, LU, PL, MT (8) But information does seem to be available for LU (link and link), HU - APSIS system (link), and IT (Veneto). There also seem to be companies like Agroptima which provide a paid service for LPIS data. EUROSTAT also maintains a list of 179 crop codes, used in their Farm Structure Survey for all farmers in their periodic surveys. These codes may be useful as an additional cross-mapping layer to HCAT3, although there are concerns that some of the HCAT3 codes are rather old, and are not useful for agroforestry (which shares the same code as forestry).

⁷ High value data, introduced by [Directive \(EU\) 2019/1024](#) (so-called Open Data Directive), are defined as data whose reuse can be associated with important benefits for society, the environment and the economy. To this end, the Directive has identified six categories (geospatial data, earth observation and environmental data, meteorological data, statistical data, business and business ownership data, mobility data). [Implementing Regulation \(EU\) 2023/138](#) specifically defined IACS agricultural and reference parcels as **being in scope** of the Open Data Directive. **Cadastral parcels** are also included. **The date for compliance with the Implementing Regulation was 9.6.24.**

Table 8: Detailed analysis of compliance with the six criteria of the DG CONNECT High Value Datasets Regulation (2023/138)⁸

Member State	Data Holder (Paying Agency)	Free of Charge	Licence	Machine-Readable Format	API Access	Bulk Download	Up-to-Date	Overall Assessment
Austria	Agrarmarkt Austria (AMA)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Fully Compliant
Belgium (Flanders)	Agentschap Landbouw & Visserij	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Non-Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant
Belgium (Wallonia)	Organisme Payeur de Wallonie	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Bulgaria	State Fund Agriculture	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant
Croatia	Agency for Payments in Agriculture, Fisheries and Rural Development (APRRR)	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant
Cyprus	Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organization (CAPO)	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Non-Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant
Czechia	State Agricultural Intervention Fund (SZIF)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Denmark	Danish Agricultural Agency	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Estonia	Agricultural Registers and Information Board (ARIB/PRIA)	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Finland	Finnish Food Authority	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
France	Agence de services et de paiement (ASP)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Largely Compliant
Germany	Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) & 16 Länder Agencies	Partially Compliant	Non-Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Highly Fragmented & Partially Compliant
Greece	Payment and Control Agency for Guidance and Guarantee Community Aid (OPEKEPE)	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant
Hungary	Hungarian State Treasury	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant
Ireland	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Italy	Agency for Payments in Agriculture (AGEA) & Regional Bodies	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Non-Compliant	Highly Fragmented & Partially Compliant
Latvia	Rural Support Service (LAD)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Lithuania	National Paying Agency (NMA)	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant
Luxembourg	Service d'Economie Rurale (SER)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Fully Compliant
Malta	Agriculture and Rural Payments Agency (ARPA)	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Non-Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant
Netherlands	Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Poland	Agency for Restructuring and Modernisation of Agriculture (ARMA)	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant	Partially Compliant
Portugal	Institute for the Financing of Agriculture and Fisheries (IFAP)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Romania	Agency for Payments and Intervention in Agriculture (APIA)	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant	Non-Compliant
Slovakia	Agricultural Paying Agency (PPA)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Slovenia	Agency for Agricultural Markets and Rural Development (ARSKTRP)	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant
Spain	Fondo Español de Garantía Agraria (FEGA) & 18 Regional Bodies	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant but Fragmented
Sweden	Swedish Board of Agriculture	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Partially Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Largely Compliant

⁸ MS were expected to report on their implementation of the HVD Regulation by February 9, 2025, and every two years thereafter.

5.3 Availability of LPIS environmental and farming constraint designations

DigitAF Deliverable 1.2 (Kay et al. 2024) suggests a range of EU agri environmental indicators that could be collected at parcel or farm scale, enabling an evaluation of the environmental impact of CAP agricultural interventions. The availability of agricultural and environmental data in the EU is explored in EURAF Policy Briefings 69 (Lawson, Muraru & Kay 2024) and 70 (Lawson & Muraru 2025), and in the publication *EU Agroforestry Futures* (EURAF 2025).

The biodiversity indices proposed for agricultural land in the Nature Restoration Regulation (2024/1991) include broad-scale butterfly (on grassland) and bird counts, which are hard to record at plot scale, but there are three which could be calculated and recorded at plot-scale: a) "landscape feature area" (Impact Indicator 21), b) soil organic carbon on agricultural soils (Impact Indicator 11) and c) soil erosion by water (Impact Indicator 13). These, and other plot-scale indicators, could potentially be linked to agri-environmental "payment by results" schemes (Reed et al. 2014; Alliance Environnement 2019).

Farmers may be limited in their opportunities to plant trees by **environmental designations** like Natura 2000 or nitrate sensitive zones. They may have access to additional CAP funds if their land is designated an Area of Natural Constraint (previously Less Favoured Areas). Environmental designations are summarised here. Some countries include this information in LPIS data - all should.

Information on environmental Indicators and the degree to which information could be calculated and held at parcel-scale is given in Deliverable 1.3 (Kay et al. 2024) and EURAF Policy Briefing #69 (Lawson, Muraru & Kay 2024). Table 9 gives a summary:

Table 9: Impact Indicators which could be recorded at farm and parcel scale (Lawson, Muraru & Kay 2024)

No	Index	Comment
I.10	Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture:	Uses national GHG emission calculations which vary greatly and are usually published only at a national level (NUTS 0). Only a few MS estimate the impact of woody vegetation outside forests separately.
I.11	Soil organic carbon in agricultural land	Based on the LUCAS soil survey therefore not available at farm or parcel scale. Averaged to NUTS2
I.12	Sustainable production of renewable energy from agriculture and forestry	Indicator is published at national (NUTS 0) scale
I.13	Soil erosion by water	Scale is different between countries. Usually only published at regional scale (NUTS2)
I.14	Ammonia emissions from agriculture	Based on manure management and fertilisation, but doesn't include the effect of ammonia sorption by agroforestry. Published only at national scale (NUTS 0)
I.15	Gross nutrient balance (N,P) on agricultural land (kg N & P/ha/yr) all MS.	Reports separately for the potential threat of nitrate and phosphorus on arable land and groundwater. Reports separately for cropland, grassland and permanent crops, but again availability is at the NUTS 0 level, and not for
I.16	Nitrates in groundwater	Reports percent of water stations with nitrate concentration over 50mg/l (per Directive 91/676/EEC) - frequency of sampling and the density of the monitored stations vary from country to country, as does the number of sampling stations over the years. May be published at river basin level.
I.17	Water Exploitation Index +	Reports % of water use over the renewable water resources available), only available at national level, or sometimes for river basins.
I.19	Increasing farmland bird populations.	Available at country (NUTS 0) level only. Species basket differs between countries, although a weighted EU basket exists. Most species will benefit from hedgerows and trees but other species (e.g. skylark and lapwing) prefer open land - therefore a less integrated index is needed.
I.20b	Percent of species and habitats of community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends	Only available at NUTS 2/3 level and relates to broad habitat types
I.20a	Percentage of pollinator species of community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends	Only available at NUTS 2/3 level
I.21	Agricultural land covered with landscape features	Currently only available at NUTS 3 (province) level based on LUCAS data from the JRC, or for woody landscape features based on Copernicus from the EEA

5.4. LPIS Aggregation Tool

The DigitAF partner Regenfarmer has developed a LPIS Aggregator web-viewer to allow inspection of LPIS data for multiple Member States. So far, information has been included from 10 administrations: AT, CZ, FR,

BE-FL, NL, DK, IE, FI, DE (NS, BB), and PT (Figure 2). Zooming to individual parcels is possible, giving details on the area, land use and crop codes in each parcel. It is intended to release the Aggregator by June 2025.

In some Member States boundary features like hedges or windbreaks (called “woody landscape features”) are recorded in a separate LPIS GIS layer. This was called the Ecological Focus Area (EFA) Layer in the previous CAP (Luketić et al. 2015). In the present CAP it is possibly called the “Landscape Feature Layer”, and may be used by some MS to record CAP Impact Indicator 21 (“Area of Landscape Features”). In most Member States this layer is being incorporated in the main Land Use layer of the LPIS, but this remains to be confirmed.

Figure 2: DigitAF LPIS Aggregator. Hovering on parcels provides location, area, land use and crop codes, Other countries will be added as stable data and licence information becomes available.

6. Corine Land Cover Data - an ecological approach but not focused on farmers

The EU DigitAF project has used Copernicus 100m % tree Cover Density (TCD) data together with Corine grassland and cropland codes to come up with a "tree-desert-index" of areas where new agroforestry planting should be prioritised. This is the basis of the EURAF/DigitAF maps of tree-planting priority areas in Europe at 100m (Figure 3) and NUTS3 scales (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Tree cover density (% tree cover in 100 m pixels) in cropland/grassland in the 39 EEA countries. The deep red areas are priority planting areas where tree cover density is particularly low. They are usually on mineral soils where agroforestry will make the greatest contribution to carbon sequestration. Copernicus tree cover density 2018 superimposed on CORINE agricultural land 2018. Each pixel in this map covers 1ha. (Lawson et al. 2023)

The first version of the EFI “tree desert” map was published in the 2020 EURAF Policy Briefing #2 (den Herder et al. 2020b). EFI and Planet Inc. repeated the process using the 2018 rather than 2015 Copernicus TCD 100m dataset - see EURAF Press release (Feb 2024) (Figure 3). This used only the Corine codes for **arable land and permanent grassland**, and excluded permanent crops like olives and orchards.

There is much more to be done to improve this index at an EU level, and DigitAF intends to replace the 100m Copernicus Tree Cover Density product with the 10m version and to use LPIS data rather than Corine. Again, an "integrated rural land-parcel-registry" would greatly facilitate this move to land-diversity mapping and potential CAP "payment by results" schemes.

The COPERNICUS "small woody feature" product was not used since the "woody mask" is manipulated in several ways and excludes tree-blocks greater than 0.5ha, irrespective of the forest definition used in national laws, UNFCCC reports and in the designation of CAP landscape feature

To meet the agreed annual LULUCF target of -310 Mt CO₂e in 2030, an average of 58.8 million hectares of agricultural land would need to be converted to agroforestry systems in the EU, ranging from 16.9 million ha (systems with many trees) to 550 million ha (systems with few trees). Eurostat reported that EU farms used 157 million hectares of land for agricultural production in 2020, or 38 % of the total land area of the EU (Eurostat 2022). This means that around 38% of the land currently used for agriculture must be converted to agroforestry in order to achieve the full LULUCF targets. This assumption is assuming steady-state production for agroforestry systems, but, as shown in Section 9, this steady state takes many years to be achieved.

6.1. Land availability for agroforestry in the European Union

Den Herder et al (2020a) suggested that the 3 billion “additional” trees, announced in the EU Forest Strategy 2030 should be primarily focused on areas “outside forests” - i.e. agroforestry in agricultural areas and trees in settlements. They used the Copernicus Tree Cover Density 2015 product⁹, and the Corine Land Cover 2018 database (providing an “agricultural” overlay) to identify areas of agricultural land which have very low existing tree cover. They also overlaid Natura 2000 and Ramsar databases to exclude protected areas. Their initial focus was on agricultural areas with zero tree cover across the wider Europe (EEA-39¹⁰), and they concluded that these “tree-deserts” should be the priority areas for tree planting or increasing tree cover through natural regeneration. These areas are usually associated with high environmental-stress indices such as erosion, low soil-carbon, nutrient loads in water courses, soil moisture deficits, and low levels of landscape or functional biodiversity (Kay et al. 2019). The three billion trees were judged to bring greater environmental benefits in these areas than continuing with conventional afforestation methods and areas (which often already have high soil organic matter). Agroforestry planting would also help achieve the Earth Commission goal of having 20-25% of natural ecosystems in each 1 km² of the earth's surface (Rockström et al. 2023), and the EU Biodiversity Strategy target of 10% “high diversity landscape features” on agricultural land by 2030 (DGENVI 2020)¹¹.

In the present study, we use the same methodology as den Herder et al (2020a), and make an updated estimate of the current extent of tree cover in agricultural land in the EU-27 using the more recent Copernicus Tree Cover Density 2018 product.

The updated calculations for EU27 (Table 11) and tree-desert map (Figure x), show that, currently, about 99.3 million hectares of agricultural land, excluding Natura 2000, in the EU-27 (2023) has 0% tree cover. This is equivalent to 59.3% of all agricultural land. An area of 106.3 million hectares (63.4%) of agricultural land has less than 1% tree cover. An area of 129.3 million hectares (77.2%) has less than 10% tree cover (Table 5).

Table 10: Area (million ha) of agricultural land EXCLUDING Natura 2000 areas in the EU27 member states with 0%, ≤1%, ≤2%, ≤5%, ≤10% tree cover for the year 2018, using 100m tree crown cover density from Copernicus and agricultural land cover from Corine.

Tree cover	Area (million ha)					Total area
	0%	≤ 1%	≤ 2%	≤ 5%	≤ 10%	
CORINE class						
211 Non-irrigated arable land	70.3	73.4	75.4	79.0	82.6	91.7
212 Permanently irrigated land	12.9	14.5	15.6	17.7	19.9	27.6
213 Rice fields	2.9	3.0	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.6
231 Pastures	0.446	0.455	0.461	0.472	0.482	0.507

⁹ Tree cover density data is provided by Copernicus in a range from 0-100% for the 2015 and 2018 reference years. The data is available as raster data in European projection ([EPSG: 3035](#)) with 20 m and 100 m resolution. For the assessment, data with 100m resolution were used to identify large areas with little or no tree cover. Thresholds of (0%, ≤1%, ≤2%, ≤ 5%, ≤10%) were identified.

¹⁰ EEA39 refers to the following countries: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom.

¹¹ The final text of the NRR ([2024/1991](#)) removed all mention of the previous 10% landscape feature target. Member States are now expected to set their own targets, involving an increase from current levels.

244 Agroforestry	0.207	0.296	0.365	0.540	0.812	2.439
Sub-total	86.7	91.6	94.6	100.9	107.1	125.8
2 All agricultural areas	99.3	106.3	110.8	119.8	129.3	167.6
Proportion (%)	(59.3)	(63.4)	(66.1)	(71.5)	(77.2)	

* Note 1: all categories exclude agricultural areas covered by Natura20000.

† Note 2: "All agricultural areas" includes Corine 211, 212, 213, 244 (above) plus areas not considered capable of supporting additional trees, viz 221 Vineyards, 222 Fruit trees and berry plantations, 223 Olive groves. 241 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 242 Complex cultivation patterns, 243 Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation, and 244 Agroforestry areas.

For non-irrigated arable land (Class 211), 70.3 million hectares (76.7%) has zero tree cover, and 9.1 million ha (9.9%) of this land has more than 10% tree cover (Table 10). Other arable classes have similar low levels of tree cover, and pastures have a particularly low tree-cover (446 thousand hectares or 87.9% of the total area of pastures has 0% tree cover). Table 10 also shows that 812 thousand hectares (33.3%) of *agroforestry land*, as identified in the CORINE database, has tree crown densities below 10%. This identifies a need for the regeneration and management of traditional agroforestry systems, in addition to the planting of new areas.

6.2 Effect of including Natura 2000 areas

Table 11: Area (million ha) of agricultural land **INCLUDING** Natura 2000 areas in the EU27 member states with 0%, ≤1%, ≤2%, ≤5%, ≤10% tree cover for the year 2018.

Tree cover	Area (million ha)					Total area
	0%	≤ 1%	≤ 2%	≤ 5%	≤ 10%	
Corine class						
211 Non-irrigated arable land	75.8	79.2	81.3	85.3	89.1	99.1
212 Permanently irrigated land	15.4	17.3	18.5	20.9	23.5	32.7
213 Rice fields	3.2	3.3	3.4	3.5	3.7	4.0
231 Pastures	0.579	0.592	0.599	0.612	0.625	0.657
244 Agroforestry	0.273	0.389	0.480	0.708	1.066	3.309
Sub-total	95.3	100.8	104.3	111.0	118.0	139.8
2 All agricultural areas	108.9	116.6	121.5	131.5	142.1	185.7
Proportion (%)	(58.7)	(62.8)	(65.4)	(70.8)	(76.6)	

When we look at the area of agricultural land **including Natura 2000**, we see that 108.9 million hectares (58.7%) of all agricultural land has 0% tree cover and 131.5 million hectares (70.8%) has less than 5% tree cover (Table 11).

A typical tree-planting density within a silvoarable system may be around 200 trees per hectare. For silvopastoral plantings, even with high quality planting material, the final stocking is typically higher, and the initial tree density may be around 400 trees per hectare. Taking the "priority area" (i.e. zero tree cover) of 86.7 million hectares of agricultural land outside Natura 2000 areas (Table 12), **these planting densities lead to a planting-requirement of 17.5 billion additional trees** (Table 12). This is a figure which: a) greatly exceeds the 3 billion "additional trees" by 2030 target in the EU Biodiversity Strategy (DGENV 2020); b) far exceeds the modest achievement of the 3-billion-additional-tree programme of 12.5 million trees planted

by October 2023; and c) enormously exceeds the total afforested and agroforested area in CAP programmes of all Member States during the period 2014-2022 of ~165 kha¹².

Table 12: Calculated “Priority” areas for agroforestry (outside Natura 2000 areas) to be planted or regenerated before 2030 (for the EU27). Planting densities assume a selective thinning rate of 3-4:1 to reach final stocking.

Scenario	Corine class	Calculated area (million ha)	Planting density (Trees ha ⁻¹)	Total trees (billion)
Priority areas (areas with 0% tree cover)	211 Non-irrigated arable land	70.3	200	14.06
	212 Permanently irrigated land	12.9	200	2.57
	213 Rice fields	2.9	200	0.58
	231 Pastures	0.446	400	0.18
	244 Agroforestry	0.207	400	0.08
Total		86.7		17.47

Planting agroforestry systems can overcome many of the land use constraints faced by afforestation, since planting 10% tree cover on agricultural land does not involve a change in land-use with the resulting changes in land value. The areas in Europe with the lowest tree cover (0-1%) on agricultural land in Figure 3 should be the priority areas for “agroforestation” (Kay et al. 2019). In the EU-27 this covers 86.7 million hectares of agricultural land outside of Natura 2000 (Table 12). So, a programme of planting 1 million hectares of agroforestry per year would take about 87 years to cover the EU agricultural land (pixel size is 100 m x 100 m) which currently has no tree cover, before starting on the areas with less than 1% tree cover. In Section 5 we ask what contribution this impossibly large annual agroforestation programme would make to the net emissions targets needed to achieve climate neutrality by 2040, and the EU target of -310 million tonnes CO₂ equivalent (Mt CO₂e) sequestration in the Land Use Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector by 2030.

Maps are also available as interactive NUTS3 averages (Figure 4), where the tree cover on agricultural land can be interrogated for each “county”. This data was ranked to show Member States with most “tree-deserts” on agricultural land. The fewest tree-deserts were in Portugal, Sweden and Slovenia and most in Romania, Cyprus and Malta (Table 13). Countries with the lowest area of “tree-deserts” are those with the greatest area of agroforestry (Lawson, Muraru, Bertomeu, et al. 2024).

Table 13: Zero-tree-index ranking of EU Member States (i.e. % agricultural hectares with zero trees) (Lawson et al. 2023)

	PT	SE	SI	IE	FI	LV	AT	FR	DE	LU	EE	BE	IT	DK	ES	PL	CZ	HR	SK	NL	EL	HU	BG	LT	RO	CY	MT
TDI	48.0	49.4	53.5	59.1	59.5	61.7	61.9	62.4	64.0	64.9	65.1	65.3	67.3	70.1	70.1	70.2	71.2	71.4	71.4	75.2	76.1	77.7	79.3	81.8	82.2	87.9	95.2
#	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27

¹² Communication by the EU Commission to the 11.9.23 meeting of the EU Forest and Forestry Stakeholder Platform “Planned afforestation at start of programme (M8.1) = 642.5 kha; achieved by Feb 2023 = 160.7 kha. Planned agroforestation (M8.2) at start of programme = 85.0 kha. achieved by Feb 2023 = 4.12 Kha.”

Figure 4: Tree deserts in Europe at NUTS3 ("county-province") level. Darker areas have fewer trees.

More detailed studies in Finland have shown that much of the tree cover attributed to agricultural land in Figure 3 is due to the overlap of 100m pixels between forest and agricultural land. This is not an error however, since it still shows the mosaic of small areas of forest in countries like Finland.

It was decided not to repeat the Corine versus TCD exercise using the Copernicus 10m dataset, since the minimum mapping unit of Corine is 25ha, which is too coarse to be comparable.

7. JRC EUDR Forest Map 2020 - exporting Europe's forest classification to the world at 10m resolution

The EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) (2023/1115) comes into effect on 30/12/2025, having been delayed for 12 months to allow more time to implement the necessary procedures and maps. It imposes strict rules on all companies wishing to place affected products on the European market, or to export them. It also applies to all EU Member States. Products must be deforestation-free, produced in accordance with relevant local legislation, and covered by a due diligence statement (with geospatial location information). Products covered are: cattle, cocoa, coffee, oil palm, soya, wood, and rubber. **Agroforestry areas are explicitly excluded from these requirements** (European Commission 2025).

DigitAF and a related project called DISTENDER undertook a detailed comparison of the EU-JRC map of "forest" in the Spanish region of Extremadura with the LPIS (SIGPAC) map of agricultural and forestry parcels. The two datasets were compared at 10m pixel resolution, showing that only 20% of "forest land" shown in the EU-JRC map was also recognised by the SIGPAC as being forest (Figure 5 and Table 15).

SIGPAC is based on CAP records and subsidies for agricultural use. It will inevitably be more accurate than the JRC forest map, which is almost entirely based on remote sensing.

Evaluation "deforestation" and (eventually) "degradation"¹³ as part of the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) is based on the very broad brush FAO definition of "forest land" superimposed on Copernicus data.

National Forest Inventories or National GHG Inventory Reports to the UNFCCC, are not taken into account.

Figure 5: Areas of "forest" identified by the JRC "Forest Observatory" in the Spanish region of Extremadura (colours) and "non-forest" (gray). matching the data shown in Table 8

In Europe, the CAP-IACS-LPIS data is likely to be a much more reliable estimate of "forest" area and can integrate with LULUCF and NFI datasets (Lawson 2023b)¹⁴. At the very least, an error analysis should be done of the changes involved in using the FAO forest definition rather than one based on national definitions and the rural land-parcel registry (i.e. national LPIS systems).

¹³ According to the EUDR "forest degradation" means "structural changes to forest cover, taking the form of the conversion of primary forests or naturally regenerating forests into plantation forests or into other wooded land, and the conversion of primary forests into planted forests (Article 2 - 7)". This is **very difficult** to gauge from remote sensing alone.

¹⁴ See this [joint statement](#) by EU timber producers and importers

Table 14: Area (ha) identified as "forest" in the EU Forest Observatory for Extremadura and the distribution of this total forest area (968,437 ha) between 5 Land Use categories identified in the Spanish Land Parcel Identification System (SIGPAC)

Uso de Suelo (ha)	JRC Bosque	JRC No Forestal	Total
SIGPAC Bosque	200,902	79,607	280,509
SIGPAC Pastizal con árboles (PA)	401,975	748,305	1,150,280
SIGPAC Pastizal con arbustos (PR)	204,386	580,468	784,854
SIGPAC Pastizal (PS)	14,392	398,161	412,553
SIGPAC Otros (combinados)	146,782	1,388,441	1,535,224
Total	968,437	3,194,983	4,163,421

Uso de Suelo (%)	JRC Bosque	JRC No Forestal	Total
SIGPAC Bosque	20.7%	2.5%	6.7%
SIGPAC Pastizal con árboles (PA)	41.5%	23.4%	27.6%
SIGPAC Pastizal con arbustos (PR)	21.1%	18.2%	18.9%
SIGPAC Pastizal (PS)	1.5%	12.5%	9.9%
SIGPAC Otros (combinados)	15.2%	43.5%	36.9%
Total	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

This 5-fold difference between estimates of "forest land" in Extremadura reinforces the need for the EU to have a reliable land use registry system - e.g. an extended LPIS - where the boundary between forest and agricultural land can be accurately reported on a parcel by parcel basis (Lawson, Muraru, Bertomeu, et al. 2024)

The Portuguese Partner in DigitAF (MVARC) is working with the JRC 10m forest map, overlaid LPIS data and LULUCF codes as follows:

1. **Forest Land** = JRC forest minus LPIS agriculture mask, minus settlement mask
2. **Cropland** = LPIS codes held separately for annual and permanent crops (woody)
3. **Grassland** = LPIS codes for permanent grassland (>5 years from ploughing)
4. **Settlements** = [Urban Atlas](#) / [Copernicus Soil Sealing](#) after extracting LPIS agric codes?
5. **Wetland** = Use national maps of GAEC2 (peatland) areas .. available for all MS?
6. **Other** = Land not covered by other categories (mainly mountains)

These maps will be added in V2 of this document

8. Copernicus tree crown cover density - a powerful pan-European approach

Arina Machine (a PhD student University of Leicester and honorary member of the DigitAF project), has been using Copernicus 10m Tree Cover Density (TCD) data and LPIS to estimate areas of TOF in Extremadura. The LPIS in Spain (SIGPAC) has the great advantage of fully integrating forest and agricultural areas, and is used for national LULUCF calculations. Preliminary work in Extremadura, mapping the frequency of different TCD categories in cropland, grassland and forest land use classes showed very large numbers of cropland and grassland parcels with more than 10% tree crown cover. (Figure 7), but the forest pixels had an average crown cover of less than 50%. (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Areas of cropland, forest and grassland in Extremadura obtained by overlaying Copernicus 10m %TCD data and LPIS pixel information, corrected for the area of each pixel and showing the extent of dense tree crown covers on permanent grassland and cropland parcels - the latter being explained by permanent tree crown covers on permanent grassland and cropland parcels - the latter being explained by permanent crops of fruit-tree species.

Figure 7 Overlay of LPIS (SIGPAC) agricultural and forest land in Extremadura with Tree Cover Density thresholds matching Figure 3. Arina Machine, PhD Thesis work. This is comparable to Figure 5, which directly maps the LPIS (SIGPAC) land use codes for agroforestry (grassland with trees and grassland with shrubs).

9. Greenhouse Gas Inventories - from pixel to parcel - but very slowly

This section focuses on whether Trees outside Forests (agroforestry and landscape features on farmland and trees in settlements) can contribute significantly to the EU's LULUCF 2030 sequestration target of -310 Mt CO₂e.

It will examine:

1. emission targets for Member States
2. observed rate of carbon sequestration in temperate agroforestry systems;
3. potential impact of the Carbon Removals Certification Framework Regulation
4. recording by Member States of trees outside forests in their annual GHG inventories.

9.1. Emission targets for EU Member State

The revised Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation became law on 11 May 2023. It set an annual Union sequestration target of -310 million tonnes per year CO₂ equivalent (e) for the LULUCF sector by 2030. This is an increase of 16% from the estimated annual sequestration of -268 Mt CO₂e in the EU in the 2016-18 base years¹⁵, and an increase of 46% compared to the level of sequestration of -212 Mt CO₂e provisionally estimated for 2021 (EEA 2022). It is significantly less than the net emission of non-CO₂ greenhouse gases from agriculture which was +382 Mt CO₂e in 2020 (EEA 2022).

Originally, the Commission's proposal included a net zero target for the whole AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use) sector by 2035. This was rejected by Parliament (Lawson 2022a), but it was agreed by Council that *"the Commission will submit a report within six months of the first global stocktake under the Paris Agreement (i.e. September 2023¹⁶)*, on including non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture in the scope of the Regulation and the setting of post-2030 targets for the land-use sector". In February 2024 the EU Commission issued this report and confirmed their plan to reduce net GHG emissions by 90% relative to 1990, but failed to set a target for the AFOLU sector.¹⁷

The -310 Mt CO₂e LULUCF 2030 target is proving very difficult for EU member states to achieve. National projections show a decrease in the level of net GHG removals, with an average of only -200 Mt CO₂e sequestered per year for the period 2020-2040 in the LULUCF sector, compared to the historical average of -300 Mt CO₂e per year from 1990 to 2019. The EU Climate Advisory Board stresses that the EU's biogenic carbon pools decreased by 35% between 2013 and 2021, of which 90% resulted from a decline in storage on forest land. However, the capacity of biomass and soil to remove carbon is forecasted to be increasingly affected by climate impacts, including droughts, wildfires, storms, pests. Additional measures planned by Member States are only expected to increase net removals from 2020 to 2040 by 3% (EEA/IIASA 2023). Much more ambitious afforestation targets are needed, but the collective afforestation programmes reported in the CAP Strategic Plans for 2023-2028 fall far short of historical averages, let alone future needs.

It is therefore our view that a sequestration contribution from Trees outside Forests of -80 Mt CO₂e will be vital to achieve net-zero in the land sector by 2040, and for this to happen an emergency agroforestry

¹⁵ LULUCF sequestration continues to decline in the EU - in 2020 it was only -239.2 Mt CO₂e (UNFCCC), and the EEA estimates that it may be as low as -212 Mt CO₂e in 2021.

¹⁶ <https://unfccc.int/documents/631600>

¹⁷ see EURAF press release on [6.2.24](#) regretting that the target of neutrality in the AFOLU sector by 2035 was removed

planting programme of 1 million hectares per year will be needed. This compares with the current planned afforestation and agroforestation programme in the EU-CAP 23-29 for all Member States of less than 0.7 Million ha over a 7-year period. For afforestation and agroforestation to make the necessary additional contribution of -80 Mt CO₂ to the 2040 AFOLU target, it is recommended that **Member States increase their annual tree-planting targets by at least a factor of 10, starting from 2025.**

9.2. Carbon Removals from temperate Agroforestry

Agroforestry systems can be highly productive carbon-sinks and are therefore suggested as one of the best measures for climate change worldwide (Terasaki Hart et al. 2023; Almaraz et al. 2023). There are a wide variety of agroforestry systems across Europe: differing according to the biogeographical region (Atlantic, continental, Mediterranean), the tree / shrub species and their density, and the products produced (fruit, wood, energy). Each system has a different potential for carbon sequestration and long-term predictions about the storage potential of agroforestry systems cannot be derived uniformly for all of Europe. They must take climatic and pedological conditions into account. Insufficient field-data on tree growth and carbon sequestration is currently available, particularly to take account of pruning, thinning and other management variables (Kay et al. 2023).

Data on the extent and condition of forests exist at a national and international level, although the consistency and completeness of data for Trees outside Forest (ToF) is rather poor (Lawson 2022b); (Lawson 2023b). Data on tree cover, tree growth and quality, and tree mortality have been collected for many decades, and in many cases are subdivided by tree species (e.g. (BWI 2012)). These forest databases are becoming more comprehensive and can already show, for example, the effects of climate change on tree growth (Marchand et al. 2023) or tree mortality (Taccoen et al. 2022). However, the growth of agroforestry systems, including individual trees, tree-lines, copses, and strips of short rotation coppices, is not covered.

This section summarises the existing (scarce) field data on agroforestry systems and breaks the data down by biogeographical region, system type (silvoarable, silvopastoral, hedges) and tree species. Some of these studies reported on whole system biomass and carbon stocks, while others included the harvesting of prunings and residues. Several combined measured and modelled data, to account for the whole lifespan of an agroforestry system – from planting to harvesting.

Table 15 gives an overview of the existing dataset and summarises the carbon storage potential by region, system and species. In total around 27 studies were found reporting on temperate agroforestry tree data (6 Atlantic, 7 Continental, 12 Mediterranean, 4 Canada/USA).

The average agroforestry system captures around 1.44 t C/ha/yr or 5.27 t CO₂/ha/yr. Systems range from 0.15-0.90 t C/ha/year in Mediterranean oak in Dehesa or Montado systems to 5 t C/ha/year in dense poplar agroforestry systems in the UK.

Even more complex is the role of silvopastoral agroforestry as a source and sink for greenhouse gases as it is strongly influenced not only by site-specific edapho-climatic conditions but more importantly, by management regimes such as herbivore type and stocking rates, duration of grazing periods, pasture management (mowing, manure application and fertiliser treatments), and the type and management of the woody component. Silvopastoral agroforestry can store significant amounts of carbon as above- and below-ground biomass, but the change in soil carbon relative to grassland without trees can vary both with site and with time from planting (Pardon et al. 2017). Trees have also been shown to produce greater

proportions of recalcitrant micro-aggregate and silt and clay fractions, which are more resilient to environmental change compared to grasslands (Fornara et al. 2018).

Several recent studies provide estimates and modelled data of the carbon sequestration rates in silvopastoral agroforestry systems across Europe (Table 15). The reported carbon sequestration rates for dehesa farms are in line with those found by recent life cycle assessments conducted in dehesas of southwestern Spain: Horrillo et al. (2020) reported an average carbon sequestration rate of 0.13 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (0.11-0.16 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹), and in an assessment of 15 extensive dehesa suckler cattle farms with 30-40 trees ha⁻¹, Reyes-Palomo et al. (2022) reported a rate of 0.9 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (ranging from 0.37-1.38 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹), with a great variability in the carbon sequestration capacity among farms and negative carbon footprint values in those farms with lowest stocking rates. Higher values of carbon sequestration (over 24 years) have been reported with silvopastoral stands of 400 trees per hectare by Beckert et al. (2016) in Scotland.

Table 15: Reported carbon storage potential of the tree component in silvopastoral agroforestry systems in Europe

	Reported carbon storage by the tree component (t C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)						Reference	
	Atlantic		Continental		Mediterranean			Mean
	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max		
Coppice trees	0.16	0.48					0.32	(2019)
Broadleaf trees	0.29						0.29	(Upson et al. 2016)
Sycamore	3.20						3.20	(Beckert et al. 2016)
Larch and pine	6.80	7.00					6.90	(Beckert et al. 2016)
Orchards	1.23						1.23	(Kay et al. 2019)
Poplar	2.78	6.35					4.57	(Kay et al. 2019)
Oaks			0.71	2.83			1.77	(2019)
Beech			0.59	2.34			1.47	(2019)
Hornbeam			0.38	1.55			0.97	(2019)
Cork oak					0.37	1.29	0.83	(2019)
Almond / Olive					1.36	1.97	1.67	(2019)
Holm oak					0.09	0.16	0.13	(Kay et al. 2019)
Dehesa I					0.11	0.16	0.14	(2020)
Dehesa II					0.37	1.38	0.88	(2022)

National LULUCF projections across the EU predict a decrease in the level of net removals from an average of -300 Mt CO₂e per year in the period 1990 to 2019 (European Commission 2021b) to an average of -200 Mt CO₂e estimated to be sequestered per year for the period 2020-2040. Additional sequestration measures planned by member states in their CAP Strategic Plans are only expected to increase net removals from 2020 to 2040 by only around 3% (European Commission 2021b). Much more ambitious targets are needed to meet the requirement to achieve net zero emissions in the integrated agriculture and forestry (AFOLU) sector. There is therefore an urgent need for the expansion of Trees outside Forest (ToF): both on agricultural land as agroforestry and in settlements as urban-forestry.

The Commission Staff Working Document which accompanied the draft LULUCF Regulation (European Commission 2021a) suggested that the 3 billion “additional-tree” target, if distributed over around 3 million hectares and assuming a planting density of 1000 trees per hectare, could potentially sequester approximately -4 Mt CO₂e per annum in 2030 and -15 million tonnes CO₂e in 2050. This means that, for every ha of trees planted in the decade 2020-2030, the Commission expects a sink of about -4.5 t CO₂e year⁻¹

in the decade 2030-2040 (i.e. 10 years after planting) and about $-7.8 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e year}^{-1}$ in the decade 2040-2050 (i.e. 20 years after planting).¹⁸

The above calculations assume a conventional afforestation planting density of 1,000 trees per ha, covering 3 million hectares in total, with 300,000 ha of annual planting from 2021-2030. Agroforestry would be planted less densely, at 150-400 trees per hectare, however the yield of carbon per individual tree will be significantly greater than in conventional forestry, with less loss of carbon through thinning operations, and continued sequestration of carbon in the soil below the trees, even in the early years of the plantation

Lawson et al (2023) report on a wide range of European and Global literature, and show total productivity of agroforestry plantations ranging from $3.37\text{-}26.8 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Table 16). A recent study for the UK Woodland Trust, by Cranfield University (Burgess & Graves 2022), modelled sequestration rates by the trees in two agroforestry systems (156-400 trees/ha) and predicted sequestration of -6 to $-18 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ over 30-40 years. Taking data for poplar planted at $156 \text{ trees ha}^{-1}$ and harvested after 30 years, using typical weather patterns for the English East Midlands, the model predicted an average annual biomass sequestration of **$-7.7 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ over a 30 year rotation**. Extrapolating this rate to the whole of Europe, and assuming that one million hectares of agroforestry could be planted annually from 2025 to 2050 indicates an average sequestration rate of 192 Mt CO_2 per year. This level of production is optimistic for the whole of Europe, however, and a figure of 5 t/ha/yr is more likely for agroforestry in northern Europe, and 1-4 t/ha/yr CO_2e in southern Europe, depending on whether irrigation is applied.

At a time when pressures are increasing to harvest greater proportions of forests for bioenergy and the bioeconomy, this contribution from agroforestry to Europe's timber supply can be very important. However, it will take some time for new plantations to become established, since : a) the full area of 25 million hectares will take 25-years to be planted; b) the volume and carbon-content of a plantation typically follows a "S-shaped" logistic curve, with growth being slow in early years, reaching maximum growth at intermediate age and declining as the trees become old and the respiration load of the stand increases.

¹⁸ These figures came from IIASA (IIASA 2023) and from the JRC. For the JRC, the net annual increment was attributed to young forests (i.e. less than 40 years old) according to a large database of growth curves collected at European level (Somogyi et al. 2008; Pilli et al. 2022) The resulting total annual volume increment was further converted to annual carbon removals by assuming an average wood density equal to 0.50 t m^{-3} , an average biomass expansion factor equal to 1.2 and an average carbon content equal to 0.5. The resulting values do not account for carbon stock change on dead wood, litter and soil, since these pools are directly affected from the land use preceding the afforestation

Table 16: Measured carbon storage potential in agroforestry systems in three agroclimatic regions in Europe and Canada / USA a) considering root biomass (roots) and b) not considering root biomass (no roots). (full data)

	Measured carbon storage potential (t C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)									References	
	Atlantic		Continental		Mediterranean		Canada / USA		Mean		
	Roots	No roots	Roots	No roots	Roots	No roots	Roots	No roots			
Hedge		1.21								1.21	(Biffi et al. 2023; Lesaint et al. 2023)
Short rotation coppice (AF = 15% SRC on field)				0.57		0.18				0.32	
Paulownia						0.18				0.18	(Zuazo et al. 2013)
Poplar				0.7						0.7	(Langhof & Schmiedgen 2023)
Robinia				0.48						0.48	(Quinkenstein et al. 2011)
Silvoarable	4.9	0.51	1.09	0.33	0.88	1.93	1.34			1.88	
Almond						0.04				0.04	(Velázquez-Martí et al. 2011)
Conifer							1.16			1.16	(Peichl et al. 2006; Wotherspoon et al. 2014)
Fruit trees			1.92	0.44						1.42	(Roberti et al. 2023; Winzer et al. 2017)
Nut trees	0.62			0.29	1.31		1.8			0.66	(Cardinael et al. 2017; Wotherspoon et al. 2014; Schindler et al. 2023)
Oak							0.8			0.8	(Wotherspoon et al. 2014)
Olive					0.6					0.6	(Lopez-Bellido et al. 2016; Proietti et al. 2014)
Poplar	5.52	0.51	1.59			3.81	1.63			3.29	(Peichl et al. 2006; Wotherspoon et al. 2014; Burgess & Graves 2022; Graves et al. 2010; Roberti et al. 2023; Upson & Burgess 2013)
Silvopastoral	1.76			2.58		1.71	1.22	0.48		1.78	
Conifer						0.21	1.22			0.71	(Gonçalves et al. 2019; Sharrow & Ismail 2004)
Fruit trees	1.76									1.76	(Cardinael et al. 2017)
Nut trees								0.2		0.2	(Cardinael et al. 2017; Dold et al. 2019)
Oak						0.15		0.75		0.25	(Gonçalves et al. 2019; Dold et al. 2019), (Zianis et al. 2019)
Olive						0.39				0.39	(Spinelli & Picchi 2010)
Poplar				2.58		5.68				3.74	(Barrio-Anta et al. 2008; Unseld 2017)
Mean	4.55	0.9	1.09	1.14	0.88	0.99	1.32	0.48		1.44	

9.3 Potential impact of the EU Certification Framework for Carbon Removals

Much interest and activity has been generated by the EU Certification Framework for Carbon Removals (CRCF) (DGCLIMA 2023) and carbon farming generally (Kay et al. 2023). Recently, DG CLIMA has published a consultancy report on options for an agriculture/forestry Emissions Trading Scheme (AgriETS) (Bognar et al. 2023) - where the main option involves the calculation of emissions for fields and farms. GHG calculations on this scale need easy access to detailed land-use information. The extent and boundaries of all fields on a farm must be available for emission estimation, together with predictions of the impact of Nature-based Solutions (e.g. agroforestry). Ideally this should use the CAP Land Parcel Information System, extended to include forestry parcels. Widening the use of the existing CAP-LPIS to all rural areas (i.e. the AFOLU-LPIS) would provide the basis of the "geospatial carbon removals registry" envisaged for 2028 in the Carbon Removals Certification Framework Regulation (2024/3012). The AFOLU-LPIS will provide: a) a link to national "wall to wall" UNFCCC reporting of emissions specified in the LULUCF Regulation 2023/839 (Bertaglia 2015) and b) an opportunity integrate environmental designations and AgriEnvironmental metrics like those from MAES (Maes et al. 2020) into a single parcel-based system (like the Farm Sustainability Compass) which can be used for CAP, NRR and GHG reporting.

The CRCF Regulation (2018/841) (aka "Union Certification Framework for Permanent Carbon Removals, Carbon Farming and Carbon Storage in Products") entered into force in December 2024, and specifically recommends use of LPIS/GSAA parcel codes to hold certification details "when available" Article 7 (sustainability) states that "*A carbon removal activity shall have a neutral impact on or generate co-benefits for all the following sustainability objectives*": climate change mitigation beyond the net carbon removal benefit; climate change adaptation; sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources; transition to a circular economy; pollution prevention and control; protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems. The impact of agroforestry on these "sustainability objectives" are described in a range of EURAF Policy Briefings such as Policy Briefing #66 on Agroforestry for Biodiversity and Ecosystems.

9.4 Recording by Member States of trees outside forests in their annual GHG inventories.

The Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) sector holds a critical position in global and national greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories. This sector functions as both a source of GHG emissions and a sink for atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂), making its accurate accounting fundamental for tracking progress towards climate targets. Recognizing this pivotal role, the European Union has established a dedicated Union-wide LULUCF target of -310 MtCO₂e of net removals by 2030, a commitment that is subsequently split into binding national targets for each EU Member State under the LULUCF Regulation (Springer & Bognar 2025). Internationally, Member States are required to provide annual GHG inventories to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC 2023b). These inventories must adhere to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, with additional guidance encouraging the application of the 2013 Wetlands Supplement and allowing for the voluntary use of the 2019 Refinement (UNFCCC n.d.). The European Environment Agency (EEA) plays a vital role in this process, compiling the aggregated EU GHG inventory based on these national submissions and ensuring consistency with international reporting requirements (Anon n.d.).

While forest land typically represents the most significant source of net carbon removals within the LULUCF sector, other land use categories, such as cropland and grasslands, are frequently net sources of emissions. The presence of woody biomass in these non-forest categories can substantially influence their overall carbon stock changes. Therefore, detailed reporting on woody vegetation —including perennial crops,

orchards, agroforestry systems, and scattered trees— within cropland and grassland is crucial. Such granular reporting is essential for a comprehensive understanding of the carbon cycle in managed lands, for identifying potential climate mitigation strategies, and for ensuring the environmental integrity of both national and EU climate targets. Without this level of detail, the full climate impact of these land management practices may be overlooked or misattributed.

This section investigates how woody vegetation in non-forest lands is accounted for. While these areas might represent a smaller proportion of land compared to forests, they can have disproportionately large carbon implications and represent a key area for climate mitigation and adaptation, particularly through the promotion of nature-based solutions like agroforestry. If woody vegetation in these categories is not accounted for, its potential as a carbon sink (e.g., through agroforestry expansion) or source (e.g., through removal or degradation) might be underestimated or misattributed within the broader LULUCF sector. This lack of specificity hinders the identification of targeted policy interventions, such as subsidies for agroforestry adoption, and complicates the accurate tracking of progress, ultimately impacting the effectiveness of climate action and the achievement of the EU's climate neutrality goals. It assesses whether woody vegetation is recorded and if its associated emissions/removals are calculated separately from herbaceous vegetation (Table 17).

9.4.1 METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR LULUCF REPORTING.

National GHG inventories, including the LULUCF sector, are prepared by Parties to the UNFCCC using the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories.³ These guidelines provide a comprehensive framework for estimating emissions and removals from various land-use categories and carbon pools. Parties are encouraged to utilize the 2013 Supplement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for Wetlands and may voluntarily apply the 2019 Refinement.

The LULUCF sector, designated as Common Reporting Format (CRF) category 4, encompasses several key land-use categories: Forest Land (4.A), Cropland (4.B), Grassland (4.C), Wetlands (4.D), Settlements (4.E), and Other Land (4.F).⁴ Additionally, emissions and removals from Harvested Wood Products (4.G) are reported.

The definitions of Cropland (4.B) and Grassland (4.C) are particularly relevant to this assessment. According to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines, cropland includes "cropped land, including rice fields and agroforestry systems where the vegetation structure falls below the thresholds used for the forest land category" (UNFCCC 2023a). National inventories often further specify this category to include "arable land, orchards" or "perennial crops" such as vineyards, olives, and other fruits. Grassland, on the other hand, typically encompasses "permanent meadows and pastures" and can also include "woody and bushy land" or "systems with vegetation that fall below the threshold of forest definition". These national interpretations highlight the varied ways in which woody vegetation might be classified within non-forest land uses.

GHG estimates within the LULUCF sector are calculated from changes in five primary carbon pools: **above-ground biomass, below-ground biomass, dead wood, litter, and soil organic carbon**. The "living biomass" pool is especially pertinent for woody vegetation, as it accounts for the carbon stored in the living components of plants. Beyond CO₂, non-CO₂ emissions, such as methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) from activities like fertilization or biomass burning, are also accounted for within this sector.

Great differences exist between Member States on whether the area of woody vegetation within cropland and grassland is explicitly differentiated, and whether its emissions/removals are calculated separately from

herbaceous vegetation . Member States are obliged to report both activity data (e.g., land area changes) and emission/removal estimates. The level of detail in these reports is significantly influenced by the methodological "Tiers" (Tier 1, 2, or 3) applied under IPCC guidelines, with higher tiers generally implying more country-specific data and detailed methodologies. Furthermore, national circumstances, including *"different allocations in national statistics, insufficient information on the national statistics, national methods, and the impossibility to disaggregate emission declarations,"* can lead to variations in how categories are allocated and reported across Parties.

The flexibility embedded within the IPCC guidelines, such as the choice of Tier levels and the allowance for national definitions, contributes to variability in reporting granularity among Member States. While this flexibility accommodates diverse national circumstances and data infrastructures, it can, at the same time, obscure the specific contribution of woody vegetation within non-forest land uses. For instance, a country employing a simple Tier 1 approach for biomass in cropland or grassland might not disaggregate woody from herbaceous components, whereas a country utilizing a more advanced Tier 2 or 3 approach, or country-specific data, might provide such detail. This means that even if all countries fulfill their basic reporting obligations, the level of detail regarding woody vegetation can vary significantly, making it challenging to draw conclusions about the area or emissions attributable to woody vegetation across the entire EU. This lack of granular comparability also hinders the ability of policymakers to understand the carbon dynamics in complex agricultural landscapes, potentially leading to less effective or untargeted policy interventions for land-based climate mitigation and adaptation strategies.

9.4.2 ANALYSIS OF EU MEMBER STATE REPORTING PRACTICES

This section provides an overview of reporting practices across all EU Member States. It facilitates a rapid assessment of commonalities, variations, and data gaps at a glance. It is the result of a quick survey of Member States National Inventory Documents (NIDs) or Simplified Review Reports (SRRs). **Detail was often lacking, and it is hoped to update this deliverable as more information becomes available** (Table 17)

9.4.3 CROSS-CUTTING ANALYSIS AND KEY INSIGHTS

All EU Member States consistently report on the LULUCF sector, including the cropland and grassland categories, as mandated by UNFCCC and EU regulations.¹ Carbon stock changes in "living biomass" and "soil organic carbon" are universally reported for these land-use categories. The methodological backbone for these inventories is predominantly the 2006 IPCC Guidelines, often supplemented by the 2019 Refinement.³ Many countries acknowledge the presence of "perennial crops" or "shrubs" within these categories in their national land classification systems or inventory descriptions.⁸ However, the carbon dynamics associated with these woody elements are frequently integrated into broader biomass calculations for the entire land-use category rather than being presented as distinct emission figures. Data gaps and methodological challenges, such as the lack of specific country-level data for certain woody vegetation types or reliance on simpler Tier 1 assumptions for less significant carbon pools, are evident across various reports.⁸ Despite these challenges, some countries, notably Croatia and Malta, are actively pursuing or planning improvements to collect more granular data on perennial crops, indicating a forward-looking approach to enhancing reporting accuracy.¹⁰

The observed variability in reporting granularity for woody vegetation within cropland and grassland, stemming from diverse national definitions, data availability, and methodological choices (IPCC Tiers), creates a "transparency gap." This gap arises because different countries interpret and quantify "woody vegetation" in non-forest contexts with varying levels of specificity. For instance, some may include only

perennial tree crops, while others might encompass broader categories like shrubs or hedgerows, and still others may not disaggregate at all. This lack of uniformity in definitions and methodological application makes direct comparisons of the climate impacts attributable to woody vegetation across Member States challenging. It hinders a precise EU-wide assessment of the climate mitigation potential of practices like agroforestry or the impact of land-use changes affecting scattered woody elements. Consequently, this complicates the accurate monitoring of progress towards the EU's LULUCF targets and impedes the development of harmonized agricultural and land management policies. If the specific carbon sequestration benefits or emission sources from woody elements in agricultural landscapes cannot be precisely quantified and compared across the Union, it becomes difficult for EU-level policymakers to identify optimal strategies, allocate resources effectively, or verify the effectiveness of policies aimed at promoting these nature-based solutions. This means the EU might be missing opportunities for targeted climate action in the agricultural sector, or misjudging the effectiveness of existing policies, impacting the achievement of its LULUCF targets.¹

To enhance the accuracy, transparency, and comparability of national GHG inventories, particularly concerning woody vegetation in non-forest lands, the following recommendations are put forth:

- **Harmonized Definitions:** It is recommended that the EU encourages or develops more harmonized, explicit definitions for "woody vegetation" in non-forest land categories, such as agroforestry systems, hedgerows, and scattered trees. Clearer, shared definitions would improve consistency and comparability across Member States' inventories.
- **Promote Higher Tier Methodologies:** Member States should be encouraged to transition towards higher IPCC Tiers (Tier 2 or 3) for relevant carbon pools in cropland and grassland, especially where woody vegetation constitutes a significant component. This would enable more accurate and granular estimation of carbon stock changes and associated emissions/removals.
- **Enhanced Data Collection and Sharing:** Support for national efforts to collect more specific activity data on woody vegetation in agricultural landscapes is crucial. This could involve detailed land-use surveys, advanced remote sensing techniques, or targeted agricultural censuses. Facilitating the sharing of best practices and methodologies, such as Croatia's planned improvements for perennial crops or Malta's successful utilization of regional project data like MediNet, would accelerate progress.
- **Increased Transparency in National Inventory Documents (NIDs):** Even if emissions from woody vegetation are aggregated within broader categories, Member States should be encouraged to explicitly detail their accounting methods in their NIDs. This includes clearly stating what specific woody elements are included in "living biomass" for cropland and grassland. Slovakia's practice of performing separate calculations for perennial cropland subcategories in their internal files, even if aggregated in the public report, could serve as a model for enhanced public transparency.
- **Targeted Research and Development:** Investing in research focused on the carbon dynamics of diverse agroforestry systems and scattered woody vegetation in European agricultural landscapes is vital. Such research would provide region-specific emission factors and carbon stock values, underpinning more accurate and scientifically sound inventory reporting.

Table 17: Summary of whether a MS report areas and emissions separately for woody vegetation in Cropland and Grassland categories

EU Member State	Reports Woody Area in Cropland	Calculates Woody emissions in Cropland	Reports Woody Areas in Grassland	Calculates Woody Emissions in Grassland	Notes/Specifics (links to be added to GHG Reports)
Austria	Not Explicitly	No	Not Explicitly	No	Tier 2. Does not explicitly report woody vegetation area or separate emissions in these categories; states "other vegetation such as shrubs and herbs are not reported". Focuses on annual crops and general grassland biomass. But a project is starting in 2023 to quantify woody biomass on croplands and grasslands (e.g. single trees/tree groups, hedgerows etc) and developing respective carbon stock change factors. PDF
Belgium	Yes	Yes	Partially	No	Tier 2. Explicitly includes "agro-forestry systems" and estimates carbon stocks for "perennial woody crops such as orchards" in cropland, using German NIR data due to lack of country-specific values. Woody vegetation is implicitly included in grassland definition. PDF
Bulgaria	Partially	No	Partially	No	Tier 1. Mentions "perennial crops" (orchards, vineyards) as 4% of cropland area, with carbon accumulation rates applied, but emissions are part of overall "living biomass" change. "Shrubs and Grasslands" (45.24% of grassland) have estimated carbon stock changes, but no separate woody emission detail. Tier 1 for dead wood/litter. PDF
Croatia	Partially	No	Not Explicitly	No	Tier 1. Mentions "perennial cropland" and uses a national value for its biomass carbon stock change. Future plans aim to provide "LUC area data for major perennial crops (vineyards, orchards, olive gardens)" to "estimate emissions for each defined crop type." No explicit mention for grassland. PDF
Republic of Cyprus	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Tier 1. grassland is divided into two subcategories: grass and woody (perennial) grassland, based on the dominant type of land cover; cropland is divided into annual cropland and woody (perennial) cropland, based on the dominant type of cultivated vegetation. PDF
Czech Republic	Unavailable	Unavailable	Unavailable	Unavailable	Tier 2. Detailed information on specific woody vegetation reporting in cropland/grassland is not available in the provided snippets, or the relevant NID sections were inaccessible. PDF
Denmark	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Cropland includes arable and tillage land, and agroforestry systems. Grassland includes rangelands and pastureland that is not considered as cropland. It also includes systems with vegetation that fall below the threshold used in the forestland category. Perennial woody crops, defined as horticultural woody crops, e.g. fruit and willow plantations, cover approx. 5 000 ha; Hedges and other small biotopes in the landscape, which do not meet the definition of forest, cover approx. 100 000 ha. These land uses are not added to the land use matrix, but they do contribute to emissions. LULC is held in 25x25m raster format. PDF
Estonia	Yes	No	Partially	No	Tier 2. Cropland includes the area of orchards. Grassland includes areas with tree cover less than 30% (not 20% as in the LULUCF Annex). Additional LU categories are not added for trees in grassland or cropland. PDF

Finland	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Tier 2. In 2023 the minimum block size for forestland was changed to 0.25ha for the whole country. 20m width is applied to linear formations. Cropland comprises the area defined as arable crops, rotational grass, set-aside, permanent horticultural crops, greenhouses and kitchen gardens. Grassland includes areas of extensive grass, ditches associated with agricultural land, areas of bioenergy plants and abandoned arable land. Biomass in apple and berry trees are accounted for but not as a separate LU sub-class in the change matrix. Carbon stock changes for trees in grassland are accounted for using Tier 2. Finland follows a similar NFI-based approach, employing a Tier 2/3 gain-loss method to estimate carbon stock changes in woody biomass on both cropland (specifically apple trees and currants) and grassland. ¹³ Their NID provides a net sink estimate for living biomass on grasslands, demonstrating that their system is capable of quantifying this pool.. PDF
France	Unavailable	Unavailable	Unavailable	Unavailable	Tier 2/3. All reports are in French .. not yet translated. PDF
Germany	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Includes “woody grassland and hedges” subclasses with separate activity factors.. PDF
Greece	Partially	No	Not Explicitly	No	Tier 1. Does not explicitly detail separate reporting or emissions for woody vegetation within cropland and grassland categories. Reports on overall biomass stock changes. Cropland identifies perennial woody crops (14 tree crops and vineyards) and non-woody crops. Grassland area is assumed to be in steady state except for areas where woody vegetation is removed. Following fires all woody grassland is assumed to regrow the following year. Different above ground stocks are assumed for shrubland and grassland without shrubs, but these categories are not entered in the land use change matrix. Greece is only country in EU which still uses the "unmanaged forest" category. PDF
Hungary	Yes	Partially	Not Explicitly	No	Tier 1. Minimum forest width of 20m mentioned rather than 10m as in other listings. Cropland contains arable lands, kitchen gardens, orchards and vineyards, as well as set-aside. and under grass - includes meadows where the production is utilised by cutting, irrespective of whether it is used for grazing sometimes, and pasture that is utilised for grazing irrespective of whether it is cut sometimes or not. Grassland includes areas with trees which are utilised for grazing and set-aside grasslands. CLC land use categories used rather than LPIS. Biomass of perennial crops calculated. Tier 1 methods applied to grasslands. PDF
Ireland	Yes	Partially	No	No	Tier 2. Cropland includes perennial woody crops (including christmas trees). Research funded into non-forest woody biomass but “questions remain in terms of establishing the carbon stock change over past years and spatial extent and management of hedgerows in the past”. The definition of grassland includes hedgerows. Inventory report says “Further research is required to complete a robust time series of hedgerow extent and condition in Ireland”, despite the first report on possible emissions from Irish hedgerows being produced in 2014.. PDF
Italy	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Tier 2. Explicitly reports on "Living biomass – perennial crops" (olives, vineyards, other fruit) in cropland, with regional-level estimation based on gain/loss rates, age classes, and growth curves. Mentions "Woody crops to other wooded land" conversion under grassland. Activity data is calculated separately for cropland and woody perennial crops, but not as a separate land use matrix. Grassland includes all grazing land, natural grassland and other wooded land that do not fulfil the forest definition (as shrublands). Organic and inorganic stocks are identified in all regions, but grassland and cropland areas are not subdivided in the land use matrix. PDF

Latvia	Partially	No	Not Explicitly	No	Tier 2. Mentions "perennial crops" in cropland and "removal of woody vegetation from naturally afforested farmlands" in conversions, but not separate emissions for existing woody components. No explicit mention for grassland. Cropland includes arable land, including orchards and extensively managed arable lands (ploughed at least once per 20 years). Animal feeding glades (periodically ploughed areas of forest used for wild animal feeding), which according to national land use classification belong to forest land. Grassland with woody vegetation has increased dramatically (1990 19.13kha, 2021 176.03 kha). Wetlands with woody vegetation also identified. Woody subclasses are not presented in the summary land use change matrix. NFI and LPIS information is routinely compared and LPIS data is regarded as definitive for cropland and grassland. PDF
Lithuania	Yes	Partially	Yes	No	Tier 2. Cropland data quantifies commercial orchards, berry plantations and willow plantations. Trees in grassland are measured in the national forest inventory, from 2012 onwards (but are not mentioned in the definition) in order to provide a "database of woody biomass accumulated in non-forest land".. LPIS is not mentioned. PDF
Luxembourg	Unavailable	Unavailable	Unavailable	Unavailable	Tier 1. Detailed information on specific woody vegetation reporting in cropland/grassland is not available in the provided snippets, or the relevant NID sections were inaccessible. PDF
Malta	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	Tier 1. Explicitly reports on "perennial crops" (vines, citrus, olives) in cropland using a Tier 1 method and external project data (MediNet). Woody vegetation is acknowledged as "permanent crops" on farms, but no separate emission calculation for grassland. PDF
Netherlands	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Tier 3. Cropland is arable land and nurseries (including tree nurseries). Intensively managed grasslands are not included in this category, these are reported under Grassland. From the NIR 2018 onwards two distinct sub-categories have been identified within the Grassland category, and these are spatially explicitly assessed. These are (1) Trees outside forests (TOF) and (2) Grassland (non-TOF). ToF are wooded areas that comply with the Forest land definition except for their surface area (<0.5 ha or less than 30 m width). These represent fragmented forest plots as well as groups of trees in parks and natural terrains, and most woody vegetation lining roads and fields. Any type of terrain that is predominantly covered by grass vegetation is reported under Grassland (non-TOF). The category also includes vegetation that falls below, and is not expected to reach, the thresholds used in the Forest land category. It is further stratified into the following sub-categories: grassland vegetation, nature, orchards.. PDF
Poland	Partially	No	Partially	No	Tier 2. "Orchards" are listed as an IPCC category within cropland, and "woody and bushy land" within grassland. However, Tier 1 is applied for dead wood/litter, and no explicit separate area or emission data for woody components within these categories is detailed. Cropland contains all agricultural land including fallow, fruit trees and orchards (bigger than 10 ares (0.1ha)). Grassland includes land permanently covered with grass, but it does not include arable land sown with grass as part of crop rotation; permanent meadows are understood as the land permanently covered with grass and mown in principle and in mountain areas also the area of mown mountain pastures and meadows. It also includes "woody and bushy" land outside the forest threshold (0.1ha, min width 10m, min tree cover 10%. PDF
Portugal	Yes	Partially	Yes	no	Tier 2. Uses Corine cropland areas - distinguishing between CL1 rainfed annual crops, CL2 irrigated annual crops, CL3 rice paddies, CL4 vineyards, CL5 olive groves, CL6 other permanent crops; grassland is GL1 all grasslands (permanent) and GL2 shrubland. Land use changes are recorded between all these categories.. PDF
Romania	Yes	Partially	Yes	No	Tier 1/2. Cropland consists of arable land, orchards, vineyards, shrub crops. The main data sources is LPIS (APIA) although movement is taking place to CLC+. Grassland includes pastures, pastures with scattered trees, hayfields, woody vegetation below the threshold of forest definition; pinus mugo shrubs; shrubs. These subcategories are not shown in the land-use matrix. PDF

Slovakia	Yes	Yes	Not Explicitly	No	Tier 1/2. Explicitly reports on "Perennial Cropland (CLP)" including vineyards, orchards, hop-gardens, and gardens. Emissions/removals are estimated for changes in woody perennial biomass stocks, with subcategories calculated separately in internal files. Grassland biomass changes are calculated, but not explicitly for woody components. Cropland has separate categories in the land-use matrix for perennial cropland and annual cropland. Cadastral units are used. There seems to be no sub-category for woody grassland. PDF
Slovenia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Tier 2. Forestland is defined using crown cover of 10% (not 30% as given in Annex II of the LULUCF regulation). Annual cropland includes arable land for annual crop production (cereals, potatoes, forage crops, vegetable crops, oilseeds, ornamental plants, herbs, strawberries, hop fields, etc), agricultural fallow land, and also temporary meadows and greenhouses. Perennial cropland includes areas for permanent crops such as vineyards, extensive and intensive orchards, olive groves, nurseries (for vines, fruit and forest trees), forest plantations and forest trees on agricultural land (this last wording is strange). Perennial grassland includes overgrown areas, "trees and shrubs", and "forest trees on agricultural land" with a minimum canopy cover of 10%. There are categories in the National Agricultural Land Use Map (ALUM) for all of these. Land use matrix changes have been calculated for three time periods using CL_a (annual), CL_w (woody), CL_a and CL_w categories based on ALUM categories (and LPIS codes). PDF
Spain	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	Tier 2. Cropland comprises all annual and permanent crops, as well as fallow land. Annual crops consist of herbaceous plants such as cereals, pulses, tubers, industrial crops and fodder crops, tubers, industrial crops and fodder crops; while permanent crops are made up of woody plants with a multiannual cycle- mainly olive groves, vineyards and fruit trees (i.e. no mention of timber/cork trees). Transitions in the area between annual and permanent crops are recorded.. PDF
Sweden	Yes	No	Yes	No	Tier 2. Reports "woody biomass stocks" referring to trees > 1.3m within cropland and grassland. States "other vegetation such as shrubs and herbs are not reported." Emissions are part of overall living biomass calculations, not separately from herbaceous. Cropland is regularly tilled agricultural land. There is no specific category for woody grassland. Land use change and carbon pool changes (e.g. living biomass, dead wood, mineral soil) are measured using Approach 3 - with 30,000 sample plots. Woody vegetation in grassland and cropland plots will be represented in this 5-yearly sampling. There are no subcategories in the LUC matrix. PDF

10. Exploiting orthophotos and LiDAR to map individual trees

The ToF resource can be very large. Recent research by the English Forestry Commission shows that 30% of the tree cover in England is outside forests (Figure 8), and a similar situation may exist in many parts of Europe.

Figure 8: Trees outside forests in England (forests in England have a minimum size of 0.1ha - (NCEA 2025)

Trees both inside and outside forests are important features of many ecosystems. Individual tree traits are key determinants of ecosystem services including carbon storage, climate regulation and fuel wood. Many countries regularly evaluate, quantify and monitor forests using field inventories as part of national forest monitoring systems. Forest inventories are the backbone to measurement, reporting and validation (MRV) for climate change mitigation initiatives such as national level REDD+ (reducing

emissions from deforestation and forest degradation), Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the Paris Agreement and the Bonn Challenge. However, harmonizing data across countries is difficult due to differences in methodologies for reporting, data formats (e.g. the LPIS systems are not compatible between countries - see DigitAF deliverable D1.4 (Tomás et al. 2025)). In some cases, the data is not available: for instance, Copernicus data is not available in the United Kingdom and Iceland. In addition, European MRV methods cannot be applied outside Europe as the data coverage only applied to Europe making global comparisons difficult. In many northern countries, sample-based forest inventories are often accompanied by airborne LiDAR campaigns, providing detailed information on the carbon stocks of forests. However, field inventories and LiDAR campaigns are expensive and labour intensive, resulting in trade-offs between accuracy, reproducibility and the frequency of reporting. In many **tropical countries**, financial and human resource constraints limit the coverage and frequency of the field inventories. In **many northern countries**, methodological differences and complexity, and differences in data availability, compatibility and interoperability pose challenges to the use of the available methods. Reiner et al. (2023) proposed an approach for rapidly and accurately mapping individual trees and quantifying their carbon stocks at national scale. In their paper, they illustrate how the challenges for Africa can be addressed with efficient new monitoring tools using Rwanda as a demonstration. The method was also tested on a small scale in Tanzania and in France and produced promising results. We believe that the method could solve also some of the challenges for estimating the area covered by agroforestry in Europe, and as a next step we will test some of the methods proposed by Mugabowindekwe et al. (2024; 2023) and various algorithms for identifying trees.

In their assessment, the authors used aerial images and map both crown size and carbon stock of each individual overstory tree in Rwanda, regardless of ecosystem type. They defined trees as woody plants visible from above and with a crown size of at least 0.25 m^2 and a visible shadow. Aerial images with a spatial resolution of $25 \times 25 \text{ cm}^2$ were acquired covering the entire country. A deep-learning model was trained using 97,574 hand-labelled tree crowns and then used to map 355,268,345 trees with crown size $>0.25 \text{ m}^2$ (excluding understory). More detailed information on the methodology and the algorithm for identifying tree crowns is available here.

In a first attempt, the DeepForest tree detection algorithm was tested on orthophotos with a 30 cm resolution from Portugal. As a first impression, the method seems to work somehow and even though the results are not yet totally satisfactory, the method seems to work less well for tree lines (Figure 9) than with scattered trees (Figure 10). Further testing of the method will continue over the coming months.

Figure 9. Linear tree formations in Portugal - with the DeepForest algorithm failing to match well

Figure 10. Agroforestry landscape in Portugal- with the Deepforest algorithm providing a better match.

This high resolution mapping, combined with digital terrain models allows the creation of "digital twins" of villages or groups of villages and can be used for catchment and sub catchment modelling using (for example) a QGIS interface for SWAT models (Kreig et al. 2019). Tree planting on contours, together with berms/swales, can act as green barriers and increase infiltration of water into the soil and absorption of excess nutrients in perennial vegetation. This could be extended to design rows of trees in herring-bone or Keyline design patterns to divert flood-waters to areas where they do less damage. This tool would be available for river basin planners and others who are developing solutions to increase rainfall infiltration in upper catchments and designing flood control measures in lower catchments.

11. EU Legislation - getting ready for the "Farm Sustainability Compass"

The GreenData4All initiative (European Parliament 2024) is intended to evaluate the implementation by Member States of the INSPIRE Directive (2007/2/EC) , and Public Access to Environmental Information Directive (2003/4/EC). It is planned to "assist Europe's green and digital transformation by updating EU rules on environmental geospatial data and on public access to environmental information". It aimed to greater sharing of data between the public & private sectors and with the general public, and "unlock the full benefits of data sharing for data-driven innovation and evidence-based decisions". The GreenData4All is not included in the Commission's work programme for 2025, and its future is uncertain. However, faster action is possible by enforcing compliance with the High Value Dataset Implementing Regulation (2023/138) of the Public Open Data Directive (2019/1024). This stipulated that a range of publicly-collected high-value datasets (including GSAA and LPIS) should be openly and freely available by 9.6.24, together with well documented APIs

(DG Connect 2024). At least 8 Member States do not meet these requirements (Table 8) and a "non-compliance decision" will hopefully be issued soon by DG Connect.

The Soil Monitoring Directive (2023/0232-COD) continues through triologue in the European Parliament and which aims to address transboundary impacts of soil degradation, secure equal market conditions and promote policy coherence at both EU and national levels in order to deliver on its objectives regarding climate change, biodiversity, food security and water protection. This very surprisingly makes no mention whatsoever of GSAA parcel codes, despite these being an integral part of the Farm Sustainability Tool (FaST - DGAGRI-DGDEFIS-DGDIGIT)¹⁹

Forest Monitoring Regulation (2023/0413) - which is also continuing through triologue. EURAF has published several versions of a Briefing on this regulation, where our principal criticism is that the Regulation misses the opportunity to provide data focused on LULUCF and GHG reporting and fails to emphasise the need to integrate information on forest distribution with the CAP GSAA. An example quoted in Policy Briefing #15 and Section 4 is Extremadura in Spain, where the local Forest Inventory (ref) estimates that there are 2.87 million hectares of land with "forest use", the JRC Global Forest map at 10m resolution estimates that there are 968 thousand hectares of "forest" using the FAO Forest Definition, and the Spanish GSAA-LPIS system estimates that there indeed are only 200.1 thousand hectares of "forest" - the difference being due to land use categories of "grassland with trees" and "grassland with shrubs" - both of which receive CAP area payments and are unlikely to be forests.

12. Conclusions - getting ready for large scale agroforestry carbon farming

The analysis presented in this report highlights some critical points for European land management and climate policy. Achieving the European Union's ambitious climate targets, particularly the -310 Mt CO₂e LULUCF target by 2030 and net-zero in the land sector by 2040, necessitates a comprehensive and urgent transformation. This transformation must proceed simultaneously on two interconnected fronts: a radical up-scaling of the implementation of agroforestry and a fundamental overhaul of the data infrastructure required to accurately measure and manage this transition.

The current trajectory of afforestation and agroforestation, with less than 0.7 million hectares planned over the seven-year period of the EU-CAP 2023-2029, is profoundly insufficient to meet the scale of the climate challenge. To achieve the necessary sequestration contribution from Trees outside Forests (ToF) – estimated at -80 Mt CO₂e – an "emergency agroforestry planting programme of 1 million hectares per year" is needed. This implies that Member States must "increase their annual tree-planting targets by at least a factor of 10, starting from 2025". This ambitious planting target, however, cannot be effectively realized or verified without a robust and harmonized data infrastructure. The ambitious planting targets will be unverifiable and unmanageable without robust data. This highlights a fundamental key issue for transformation: both the implementation of agroforestry and the measurement systems require a radical upgrade to be successful.

A "harmonized, standardized, and reliable estimate of the current extent of agroforestry" is urgently required to support effective policy and reporting. This necessitates further developing and harmonizing the existing Land Parcel Information System (LPIS). This registry must integrate forest parcels and agricultural parcels currently excluded from LPIS (e.g., small holdings, hobby farmers). This integrated registry could form the foundational basis for a "geospatial carbon removals registry" envisioned for 2028 under the Carbon Removals Certification Framework (CRCF) Regulation.

¹⁹ Some MS maintain that the right to confidentiality of personal data under the GDPR regulation means that the INSPIRE Directive does not apply to soil data from IACS systems (see "[Report on the national and EU regulations on agricultural soils data sharing and national monitoring activities](#)").

The establishment of such a registry would facilitate the integration of GIS systems for forestry and agriculture and enable reconciliation with national cadastres, thereby fostering a holistic view of land use across the continent. Continued investment in and harmonization of advanced remote sensing technologies, including LiDAR, high-resolution satellite imagery, and machine learning for individual tree detection, is crucial for improving the quality and comparability of ToF data. The need to integrate forest and agricultural GIS systems signals a move away from fragmented, siloed land management towards a holistic, parcel-based approach. This integration is not only a technical fix but represents a fundamental shift necessary for coherent environmental governance across the EU, enabling a truly comprehensive understanding and management of the entire landscape for climate, biodiversity, and resource sustainability.

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